

Grief Is a Human Experience, Not A Diagnosis That Needs Fixing: Clinicians Must Modify
Their Thinking and Ways of Grief Therapy

by

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DEDICATION

This is dedicated to my mom, who has always believed in me and pushed me that education was important to stand on your own two feet. To my long-time friend Dr. David Cook, big brother, friend, and mentor who has always believed in me, encouraged me, and somehow understood me. To my precious angel friends from my grief group, Ms. Judy and Claire, my lifeline back to life, there are really no words adequate to describe how impactful you both have been in my life. To Megan Devine, whose book changed my life and set all this in motion, I am getting my doctorate and setting out to change how we view grief and therapy. My husband now, Douglas Black, who has been patient with me through my tumultuous grief journey, all the emotions that my doctorate program has brought to the surface, who has honored my late husband Shane, who I lost, which takes a big man that not many a man could ever do. And most of all, my late husband, who has gone home to be with Jesus, my best friend, my encourager, my inspiration, the legacy I want to live on in learning and evolving to better help individuals as he lived to do, Shane Garrard. Like we always said to each other, “The people who are crazy enough to think they can change the world are the ones who do” (Steve Jobs). I also would like to acknowledge Dr. Thomas Schear in my doctoral program for his guidance and our shared passion for helping individuals.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

DSM- Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders

PTSD- Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder

PGD- Prolonged Grief Disorder

ABSTRACT

This dissertation seeks to analyze the various modifications that must be made in grief therapy to remove the conception of grief as a mere illness that has to be treated. Today, the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders (DSM) tends to pathologize grief as a mental disorder demanding a cure (Lund & Clement, 2021). This can be counter-productive in paradoxical ways to the therapeutic and idiographic processes of grieving, leading to coping ‘solutions’ that are unhelpful for the griever. The study calls into question the current diagnostic approach and opposes the medicalization of grief as a form of psychopathology. The limitations in current clinical practices are discussed based on a structured literature review, semi-structured interviews, and thematic analysis for a humanistic grief therapy framework. Based on interviews with participants who lost their loved ones and professionals in grief therapy, the thematic analysis presents the most important aspects of grief, which are beyond the PTSD domain criteria (Wild et al., 2023). While this dissertation rethinks the medicalization of grief, it also provides empathic methods toward the goal, where clients can express and share their individual grief narratives, which will strengthen the practice and procedure of treatment for people in the grieving process.

INTRODUCTION

Background of the Study

Grief is one of the essential aspects of life that every human being will experience in their lifetime. Grief is defined as people's vulnerable and complex reactions, moods, and actions in response to the loss (Revet et al., 2020, pp. 356-363). Grief is becoming an essential part of human life as all cultures and societies in different periods of their development have adopted certain forms of rituals or practices for mourning that are intended to help people cope with loss. However, in today's modern and clinical approaches, there is a shift to pathologizing grief, where it is seen as something that needs treatment. This transformation can be seen in exemplifying and institutionalizing Prolonged Grief Disorder in the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders (DSM-5) (Sevedge & Ann, 2021). It is suggested that our society has developed an idea of a proper way to grieve, and if individuals do not conform to these expectations, children and adults, in particular, are abnormal and need help, thus, they are medicalized.

The diagnostic approach to grief has also taken into consideration crucial importance since it affects both the bereaved and the clinicians. However, if the person has lost a loved one, getting a disorder that can be associated with the loss can feel like a form of stigma, and it may interfere with the process of grieving (Isuru et al., 2021, pp. 1-8). It can also result in the delivery of treatment protocols that assume that clients suffering from grief are inherently 'ill' and require to be prescribed suitable types of coping mechanisms rather than having to embrace those personal and cultural values that are associated with grief. From the clinicians' perspective, this approach may constrain the perception of grief and the potential treatment possibilities offered to the clients, all while returning the attention to evidencing the specific symptoms of grief rather than embracing all the aspects of the loss. This can reduce the potential therapeutic benefit of antidepressants and

maladaptive behavioral change and could be deleterious if the programs do not address the emotional and existential aspects of grief adequately.

The diagnostic model has gained much popularity recently, but new developments in grief therapy have emerged to challenge the model. Current scholars and clinicians encourage accepting grief and believe that mourning involves assessing people's unique coping and recovery processes (Meichsner et al., 2020, pp. 560-569). In this approach, there is the acknowledgment of the grieving person's stories and the need to use ideal emotions and understanding. It aims at changing the techniques used in acknowledging grief, which have so far diagnosed grief as an illness but embrace the noble and transforming process of grief. The rationale for this shift in perspective can be summed up as follows: This new paradigm is based on a body of qualitative studies that supports the notion that grief may manifest in several forms; therefore, approaches to therapy should be compatible with such variance.

This work aims to elaborate on this new paradigm in grief therapy and promote this approach (Kochen et al., 2020, pp. 1-22). This research seeks to critically analyze what has become of grief therapy today, both in its practices and its theoretical foundations, in light of the limitations that have been identified with the diagnostic approach, and more importantly, find practical ways of making a change and shift to an approach that is more in tune with the experience of the grieving persons. This prospective qualitative research intends to survey current views of loss and ways of treating it with the help of existing empirical literature and a series of semi-structured interviews with persons grieving significant loss and with practitioners in the field. Hence, the goal of the findings of this research is to help establish practices and methods of grief therapy that prove to be tender and valuable to those in need.

Finally, this research is framed by caring about grief as a human process that deserves compassion, understanding, and acknowledgment of how it transforms people's lives. Therefore, this research seeks to change the conventional ways clinicians treat grief by moving the emphasis from diagnostic thinking to therapeutic listening, from trying to eliminate presenting symptoms to helping clients bear their pain, and from proscriptive methods to individuated support (Neimeyer & Robert, 2022). The need for a reimagining of therapeutic bereavement care is called for because creating an environment that genuinely allows for coping with loss entails a different set of imaginations from what has been in place so far.

Research Problem

The research problem central to this dissertation is the medicalization of grief in present-day practice and the subsequent deficit for change to the therapy kind. The current diagnostic model, best exemplified by the inclusion of Prolonged Grief Disorder (PGD) in the DSM-5, is helpful in pathologizing grief strictly within a framework of defining what should and should not be considered as “normal” versus “abnormal” grief (Williams & Caroline, 2023). This compassionized discourse can lead to denying the common, inherently subjective, and variable responses to loss as exogenously defined and controlled. In the same respect, children who are irregular in their functioning may not fit the diagnostic criteria as spelt out in the DSM and may, therefore, be either overdiagnosed or receive treatment that may not address whatever is ailing them but compounds the misery.

Another problem of the diagnostic model is that it disregards the implications of culture, social relations, and grieving individuals' personalities. Bereavement is a complex, multifaceted process characterized by personal variables such as personality, the nature of cognate relationships, cultural identity, and available support structures. However, since clinical diagnosis assumes a

standardized model that is applied to all clients, then it is capable of missing such qualitative distinctions and may well turn an average, however rather uncomfortable, grief process into a pathological one. The above misalignment means that those interacting with the bereaved are likely to offer the wrong treatments, often prescribing medication or highly therapeutic interventions that do not recognize the individual and, frequently, the linear nature of grief.

Another issue to address is the social exclusion and extra suffering that such labeling might bring in terms of perceiving a normal reaction to stressful events as a mental disease. In particular, people who are struggling with grief illnesses may feel more rejected or stigmatized after receiving such a diagnosis, which can only worsen their suffering (Elwyn & Rosiel, 2023). Such social labels can also prevent individuals from seeking assistance because they feel like they will be judged or stereotyped. With a concentration on diagnosis, the basic tenet of therapy, namely the recognition of the patient's suffering and the desire to help alleviate it, can be lost, giving way to the medical model of targeting present symptoms and the criteria that define them.

Also, the diagnostic model can restrict clinicians' latitude, hindering them from offering compassionate care unique to the patient's condition. It is possible that due to the necessity to use the criteria and categories of the DK, therapists may have less potential to be individualized in their approach to each person who is experiencing some grief (Jankauskaite et al., 2021, pp.458-484). This could be detrimental to creativity and understanding the client's journey through the grief process, which is vital in end-of-life care. Clinicians may also find themselves squaring with the challenges of advocating for care plans that go beyond the confines of insurance and health systems regulated by diagnostic pronouncements, thus making it difficult for the patients to be given more holistic and personalized care.

Considering these challenges, this dissertation aims to examine and propose a more suitable theoretical framework for treating grief that appreciates the grief process as an intrinsic characteristic of human existence. The research will address the inadequacies of the currently predominant diagnostic approach to grieving and the proposed empathic alternative for grief therapy (Frazer & Kayla, 2022). Thus, to better qualify gaps and differences in grieving processes and to emphasize the importance of pluralistic, client-centered approaches in grief therapy, the present study employs findings from interviews with bereaved individuals and clinicians to provide an in-depth description of the participants' experiences. This research problem is academically relevant and has real-world repercussions for enhancing the experience of persons on an existential and existential journey regarding grief. In this respect, this study aims to add value to the progressive change of grief therapy and enhance and acknowledge the actuality of grief work.

Objectives of the Study

Because this study focuses on the evaluation of modern grief therapy practices and the corresponding theoretical concepts and identification of a more humane approach to understanding grief as a natural though multifaceted human phenomenon rather than a sickness, the primary method of data analysis to be employed in this study is a critical analysis of the literature (Wastell & Colin, 2020). This objective follows from the escalating awareness that the professionalization of grief, as witnessed in the classification of grief as a disorder in manuals such as the DSM-5, can be pretty unhelpful and unrepresentative in understanding the deeper, more individualized, and culturally infused processes of mourning. Therefore, the implications of the present study lie in its critique of the diagnostic approach to grief and its assertion for more compassionate, recovery-oriented, and procurement of healing practices that welcome the mourning process.

This primarily concerns uncovering and describing the phenomenology of peoples' grief therapy processes under the current diagnostic paradigm. In assessing the effects of medicalization through qualitative interviews, the study aims to identify detailed case narratives that capture the human experience of being treated within the context of medicalization (Smith & Grace, 2024). This includes the extent to which persons have been embraced in understanding their grief journey, how the clinical interventions aided or hampered their healing process, and what participants believe comprises good and caring grief therapy. At this level, the nuances are laid; hence, it helps understand the deficits and shortcomings in current practice and fashion highly personalized interventions that consist of empathy.

It is also essential to outline another significant milestone to map and consider the viewpoints of practitioners of grief therapy. This includes learning more about how different clinicians work with grief today, whether it is the theories used or the day-to-day difficulties of providing appropriate treatment for bereaved people. Based on interviews and surveys among practitioners, the study will reveal the level to which these practices are adopted from the diagnostic model and their compatibility with practitioners. It will also introduce them to other, more humanistic diagnostic techniques. This will offer a vital snapshot of the profession in which fields of training and development must be achieved to make new shifts in therapy paradigms.

The study will also seek to establish an effective research-based clinical practice protocol for practicing clinicians to suggest how grief therapy could be made less mechanical and more individual-centered. The recommendations for therapeutic practice will be built upon the data gathered from qualitative inquiry and will focus on the issues of empathy, use of personal stories, and cultural competence (Levitt et al., 2022, pp. 267-279). Its purpose is to offer concrete interventions that clinicians might employ to help their clients, targets, patients, and other

consumers of clinical services create healing surroundings that accept and respect the person's mourning instead of medicalizing it.

Lastly, this study aims to make the knowledge of grief and bereavement more available to the communities of psychology and psychotherapy (Lenferink et al., 2021, pp. 907-916). This study was developed to offer a view on the current diagnostic model and work toward a new one; therefore, its findings and conclusions aim to impact subsequent studies, legislation, and practice development. Its purpose is to expand knowledge and awareness regarding bereavement and opening and fostering approaches much closer to the grieving individual's needs and journey. In this way, this study aims to provide evidence-based findings and recommendations that would contribute to the construction of continuous and meaningful change in the way grief therapy and intervention are delivered in clinical practice so that individuals dealing with the processes of grief and mourning receive the proper support that they need during this challenging time in their lives.

Significance of the Study

It is essential to follow up with an understanding of the implications of this study, which aims to alter the current approach to conducting grief therapy by dismantling the diagnosis and medical model and embracing a more humane and patient-centered approach. The fragility of the proposed change in the current clinical practices for treating matters related to grief and mourning indicates the need to develop an alternative approach to the current process of pathologizing grief and approaches to it (Lund & Clement, 2021). Implications of this study can be applied in designing and implementing better therapeutic practices that best address the personalized and most often intricate experiences of grief, thus enhancing the way grievers are handled.

Another tremendous learning from this study is strengthening the therapeutic relationship between clinicians and their clients constructively. As such, the research supports a model that

encourages empathy, validation, and the necessity of personal and relatable stories to work on and develop an understanding and supportive relationship (Alameda & Miriam, 2020). This approach, I believe, will reduce the suffering of clients in the process and help them feel that they are being understood as unique persons who are coping with grief in different ways instead of being categorized by a newly assigned diagnosis. Building client-therapist rapport is critical for therapy since it enhances rapport and develops trust, which is pivotal for individuals undergoing therapy as they are offered the opportunity to analyze and work through their grief.

Besides, this study fills the gap in the cultural norm shaping societal attitudes and approaches towards grief. The medicalization of suffering can be viewed as a problem because it means that grieverers are categorized as sick people based on their typical reactions to a loss (Smith & Grace, 2022). Thus, the work done here questions this view, therefore contributing towards developing a more tolerant and empathetic perception of grief, which may contribute to decreasing prejudice associated with the mourning process. This, in turn, can lead to increased social support for personal grieving and grieving persons, as their experiences are not demonized but are, instead, mainstreamed and even privileged.

It also has a rich potential for implications for the training and education of professional psychology, counseling, and social work practices. As a gentler and more accepting way of understanding the grieving process, this study can inform those programs to provide a more comprehensive and sensitive foundation for future clinicians to approach mourning individuals. This may lead to the emergence of a new generation of practitioners who are well-suited to assisting clients through their grief process, thereby improving the overall usefulness of grief therapy.

Last but not least, this research will help add valuable knowledge to the current literature regarding grief and bereavement and present ideas and materials emerging from the adopted qualitative study. In this manner, the research contributes novel theoretical insights by presenting participants' experiences of grieving and practitioners' opinions to the field. This can create further exploration and debate among scholars, promoting further development of grief therapy practices. This study's relevance is not limited to the results presented herein. Still, it may bring significant long-term implications to clinical practice, social perceptions towards grieving and those who mourn, and professions in grief and loss research and training.

Organization of the Dissertation

This dissertation is divided into several chapters, each positioned to provide a full spectrum of analyses relevant to the nature and role of grief as a human phenomenon and the requirement for a new perspective in grief therapy. The structure suggested here makes it possible to organize the information sequentially and help the readers grasp the overall picture of the research problem, the methodological approach used, the results achieved, and the conclusions made. The organization also suits the interdisciplinary approach of the topic, combining the ideas of psychology, sociology, and clinics while describing grief therapy.

The need to undertake this research was informed by the research problem, objectives, and significance of the study highlighted in the first chapter of the dissertation. It describes the sequential model-based assessment of grief and its shortcomings before building a case for how grief should be understood as anew normal process. This chapter also explains the study's method and the dissertation's layout. It aims to bring the reader into the expectations and expectations of the detailed development of the work and lay the basis for the current research.

After the introduction, the next chapter, the Literature Review/Theoretical Framework, presents a literature review and theory on grief and bereavement. It provides detailed information on historical and current grief therapy methods and the medicalization of grief. This chapter also considers other frameworks encompassing the qualitative aspect of grieving besides the medical model, such as the phenomenological and humanistic models. This chapter offers a background to this dissertation by discussing a vast number of literature to augment the /for the argument for the proposed change in grief therapy.

The chapter on Methodology provided details on the research approach employed in data collection and analysis. The rationale used in selecting participants, the methods used in the data collection, and the steps used in analyzing the data to emerge with the themes and patterns are highlighted. Ethical issues are also discussed following the methodological reflection of the study to confirm that the participants were respected, and their stories valued. Out of all the chapters of the research work, the methodology chapter is perhaps the most important as it sets the overall tone of the research work by laying down basic guidelines and criteria on how the study is to be conducted rigorously and validly.

The Results and Discussion sections contain the significant arguments and conclusions that address the research objectives. The Results chapter presents a general summary of the gathered empirical paper and research findings, which are based on qualitative interviews with subjects who suffered tremendous loss and practitioners of grief therapy. The sources cited in the Discussion chapter elucidate the significance of these findings in terms of the theoretical premises and correlate the analyzed data with the existing body of knowledge. It also unfolds the possible clinical implications for various clinicians and provides recommendations for future practices and research.

Lastly, the Conclusion chapter brings together key research conclusions and stresses the need for new perceptions of grief approaches used in clinical settings. It drives home the need to view grief as a normal phenomenon and outlines specific ways to modify treatment methods to enhance the outcomes reached. This last chapter also addresses such issues as study limitations and prospects for future research to increase the knowledge and develop grief therapy. This document closes with a dedicated Reference List and Appendices sections containing a more detailed understanding of the research.

They have divided this dissertation systematically to effectively and comprehensively present the researched problem, analysis, implications, and recommendations. The arguments are presented in a clear and logical sequence, with every chapter expanding upon the issues in the previous one in a way designed to inform the reader about grief and the inadequacies of the grief therapy approach. Choosing this structured approach also improves the overall comprehensibility of the dissertation while asserting the effectiveness of the conclusion of the research.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Overview of Grief and Bereavement

Grief As a Multifaceted Emotional Response to Loss

Bereavement involves more than just simple feelings of sadness; it may be described as a comprehensive state of individual psychological, social, or even physical well-being after experiencing a loss (Seiler et al., 2020). Grief is, therefore, a phenomenon that embodies the sense of loss brought about due to the lack of a significant person or object, and its effects are feelings ranging from extreme sorrow to anger, guilt, confusion, and hopelessness. It would be difficult to partition as the moods go up and down in a cycle unpredictably and with varying degrees and lengths of time. Furthermore, grief does not only take a toll on a person's feelings, but rather it affects the whole person, and it is experienced as bodily fatigue, anorexia, difficulty in sleeping, and physical complaints (Glorioso et al., 2020, pp. 245-256). These physical signs testify to the fact that grieving is not merely a mental exercise but impact the physical self in rather noticeable ways; this further shows that the phenomenon of grieving has an avenue effect on the natural health of a grieving individual.

In addition to embodying sadness, loss, and suffering at an individual level of psychological and physiological well-being, it pervades the social and relational aspects of existence in a manner that recasts and transforms human relationships, roles, and social affiliations (Crooker et al., 2021, pp. 598-611). Such relationships ordinarily entail predictable dynamics in terms of care and companionship. Still, they are unexpectedly severed due to death, and thus, suffering grief, people are left alone, unwanted, and feel an utter void. Also, cultural norms, roles, and scripts for sadness and mourning impose additional layers to grieving as they outline how a person must or should grieve. Therefore, people can experience the feeling that they need to cover

something or even set it aside, which may cause distance from the self and others. Thus, grief no longer remains an individual process but embraces the sociocultural sphere, reflecting it and undergoing changes. Consequently, the complexity of grief puts into question the human body, mind, and spirit as it envelopes a holistic approach to healing, showing the need for sensitive and integrative intervention to assist those experiencing the complexly layered mourning process.

Natural and Universal Experience

It is worth noting that grief is one of the few experiences in life seemingly unaffected by an individual's culture, geography, or demographic status. Man, being mortal and alive the world over, no matter how old or from what part of the world or culture, is bound to encounter the death of a loved one in the life span (Ogbujah & Nnamdi, 2020). Starting with the death of the pet for the youngest child to the loss of beloved companions as a person grows old, grieving is all part of human life. It's applicable in all times and places since grief arises from human primal instincts and relation – love and attachment. Despite being in Eastern societies where grief and mourning are culturally practiced but strictly observed in private, in Western societies where people can freely and easily weep for their lost loved ones, or cultures where people must perform and organize burials differently, the experience is universal.

Moreover, the existence of grief proves that it is natural and thus helpful as a response to loss. It is present in all cultures. Cultural grief expressions and the seven stages of grief These feelings are typical in culturally diverse societies and include sadness, anger, guilt, and disbelief (Yoon et al., 2022). These emotional reactions are helpful in the process of coping and mastering the trauma, to help the individuals accept the reality of the loss, to help them verbalize their feelings, and, in the end, to find a place where the trauma fits in the individual's subjective experience of self. The generality of weeping also means that sorrow is a shared experience that

enables people to find solace and bonding when Mourning. The culture of burials and mourning is not unique to any culture, and despite the societal, traditional, or religious practices that are in place all over the world, loss and sadness are accurate and a sign that we are all in this world together as people and such instances help generate sympathy and empathy among people.

The Death of a Loved One Typically Triggers Grief

Grief is defined as a state that combines sorrow and outcome in an individual after a particular event, notably bereavement (Venkatesan & Srinivasan, 2022, pp. 619-624). However, we must realize that grief refers to the aftermath of burial or funeral and any loss. Even though one feels an enormous hole in the simple loss of a loved one, there are so many other circumstances that may prompt a cry of 'Loss.' For instance, the breakup of a relationship through a breakup or divorce is likely to occasion grief, which is made up of sadness, anger, and emptiness. Likewise, in the loss of a job or any significant career loss, people can experience grieving since they lose their identity, purpose, and financial stability that comes with the career. Moreover, any changes such as the loss of a lover one that affects health, either personally or of a loved one, is likely to cause anticipatory grief in a human being since they grieve in expectancy of an increase in decline in health condition.

While there are differences in the depth and longevity of responses to non-loss as opposed to loss, some components are similar to those of bereavement grief. The informal career can also develop symptoms of depression as well as other feelings, such as sadness, anger, guilt, and anxiety, as they cope with the new reality of their loss and changes (Noonan & Susan, 2022). Similarly, non-death-related grief is a process of accepting a change and adapting to loss in circumstances that have been changed. Furthermore, the loss value can also be relative in that it can vary depending on the individual and the factors relating to the person's attachment to the role,

the person, or a part of life that has been lost. This, in a way, makes grief okay for anyone because while grief is not a unique idea, the experiences and events that lead to it can be very diverse. Indeed, everyone deserves support and understanding as they venture through forms of loss that most people have not experienced.

The Experience of Grief

As much as it is universal, grief is defined by different sets of circumstances within the lives of various people (Davies & Douglas, 2020). Although the loss of a close one, and therefore the cause of grief, is usually tied to death, the manner of the loss is a significant determinant of grief parameters. For instance, sudden and accidental deaths may cause a great deal of shock and denial, while expected deaths due to chronic illness may lead to anticipatory grieving that consists of a combination of feelings, such as sadness, relief, and guilt. Promisingly, it also reveals the factors increasing or complicating the grieving process, such as open and unresolved issues, trauma, and more (Zulliger & Alora, 2023). Additionally, the closeness or fondness of the relationship shared with the deceased serves as the benchmark for defining the magnitude and longevity of grief. It is quite possible that close and loving relationships can elicit intense pain, such as sorrow or longing, while distant relationships that are confused and documented with conflict may bring about relief and regret.

In addition, gender, as well as other related personality and personal variables, also affect how people cope with grief and the level of coping resources and resilience exhibited (Chami, Marie & Pooley, 2023, pp. 477- 504). Others may enter the stage of change with resources that allow them to manage and respond to loss and newer experiences that come with phases of change positively. On the other hand, those with other disorders may experience difficulty in handling excessive emotions or could have abnormal long or complex processes of grieving. For instance,

individual difference variables like attitudes, gender, age, genetic make-up, prior exposure to grief, culture, and social support may all influence the mourning process. Further, audience pressure, financial instability, sickness, or social pressure may only make grieving more complicated and demanding in showing that In conclusion, it is crucial to appreciate the complexity of grief, including factors related to the grieving person, the relationship with the deceased, culture, and context.

Psychological Functions of Grief

Grief, while universally experienced as potentially catastrophic personally, inherently contributes to psychological functions that help an individual cope with loss (Russ & Victoria, 2020). Firstly, grief assists the grieving in coming to terms with the loss they have experienced. Loss: grief is one of the hardest things that people must deal with, especially when a loved one has passed away; for some people, it starts with disbelief and denial. Thus, grieving enables one to adapt to the new reality in small intervals and stages. In light of this, the realization of the finality of the loss can be accepted, thus enabling the reality of a lost loved one to be incorporated into one's scheme of things. It is a step through which one begins accepting the situation and opens the gate to recovery after the loss.

Further, they argue that grief helps to enable one to cope with loss and adapt to the new reality of living without the deceased. It is challenging to find meaning in life when one has suffered a loss and resides in a home that lacks the beloved's presence. This comprises trying to manage schedule alterations that were earlier associated with the presence of the dead. Grief allows one to mourn a state of existence centered on these Eastern cultural 'traditional' ways and slowly begin incorporating change and difference into their life (Mulemi & Benson, 2020, pp. 1520-1524). Despite that adjustment is a process replete with delicate struggles and failures, grief acts

as a sign of change and development. And through grief, people grow more robust, they gain the ability, and they gain the strength to learn how to deal with life in such a manner that their loved one cannot deal with anymore. Finally, grief serves a particular purpose in helping the process of change in one's life after the loss experience.

Historical Perspectives on Grief

Ancient and Cultural Practices

Traditionally, grieving and mourning are culturally ingrained, particularly in the mourning and burial process, where most cultural practices have secular and religious significance. The Egyptians and the Greeks, among other early civilizations, had a complex funeral ceremony that accompanied bereavement, emphasizing the societal undertone of grief and its appreciation (Planthold & Irene, 2022, pp. 562-583). These rituals were carefully planned not only to pay respect to the dead but also to open the time frame after which a specific mourning process must occur in which the people of the society can grieve together, gather their strength from one another, and find a way forward. For example, the social mourning expressions in ancient Greece included wailing and dressing as prescribed, which fostered bonding of the people in the society to benefit the deceased (Danforth & Loring, 2020). Burials had wonderful rituals, with gifts for gods, which may have stemmed from the belief that celebrating the dead was necessarily tied to the prosperity of the living. Such communal rituals pointed out that society recognized loss and the need to mourn for it, and several methods were employed to achieve this goal.

Of all the cultures worldwide, the most striking example of a mourning tradition that stemmed from the belief in the afterlife is that of ancient Egyptians. The Egyptians did not look at death as a way of potential existence gone but as an actual shift of the spirit to another realm that needed proper preparation (Agai & Matthew, 2020, pp. 17-23). Their grieving customs involved

burying, especially in the event of mummification, which was a protracted procedure meant to preserve the body of the deceased for their soul to travel to the afterlife. This was followed by many ceremonies expected to guarantee the safe journey of the dead, including the “Opening of the Mouth” rite, which aimed at awakening the corpse’s faculties in the other world. This is contained in a papyrus known as the Egyptian Book of the Dead, a series of spells and enchantments buried alongside the dead to help guide them through the perils of the hereafter (Chambers & Catherine, 2023). These practices capture concern that was placed deeply into mourning because it is believed that the deceased’s fate after passing on was predetermined by their activities while alive. With these highly detailed grieving practices in place, the Egyptians ensured that the people respected and remained actively connected with their beloved deceased. This strong cultural belief in the submission and obedience of the living to the dead is a perfect representation of how grief and rituals were concomitantly intertwined with cultural norms and expectations many years ago.

These traditions and customs show that sorrow has always been considered a vital form of human response and a shared feeling tightly woven into social life. Due to evolution and other societal factors, they presented lavish funeral rites characteristic of Egyptian and Greek civilizations that afforded a legal structure for the bereavement process while considering the grieving process and other worldliness (Zambernardi & Lorenzo, 2022). They demonstrate that there is always an ancient yearning to comprehend the orison of preparing to die, to mourn, and to assist others who are grieving in formulaic communal ways, from where one can understand the frameworks of loss as a follow-up to uncover the general imposition of mourning and the usage of cultural rites as a means of mourning. It also illustrated the need for anger, which focused on developing places for people to mourn together, along with other cultures, owing to the different

ways society dealt with grief. Altogether, these traditions help to realize that, while mourning is private and distinctive, it is more helpful if embarked on with the support of relatives and friends and accompanied by acts that are scored as valuable by the culture.

The Evolution of Psychological Theories

Funerals and grief have seen a drastic change with the emergence and growth of psychological theories specifically influencing today's perception. At the beginning of the Twentieth Century, Sigmund Freud's work on melancholia pioneered work toward understanding grief and its formulation (Meyerowitz & Rael, 2022). Sigmund Freud was the first to propose the stage model, suggesting that mourning is an intrinsic detachment from the deceased person. They should highlight how, according to Pallotti, this detachment entails a multifaceted and frequently painful process of reality-checking that the bereaved person sees as a way to come to terms with the loss. This confrontation with reality requires a structural and affective transformation as the renewal embraces the truth of the loss and the hopelessness of holding on to what has claimed a life (Demeyer, Hans & Vitse, 2021, pp. 541- 574). Freud's theory emphasized this crucial grief process, which, though painful, was a healthy process, pointing out that if this process is not followed through, it may inevitably lead to melancholia, where the individual remains stuck with the object, unable to sever the ties.

Many of the paradigms and practices of grief counseling that have evolved over the last century have their foundations in Freud's initial elucidations of grieving. It consists of opinions ever uttered by him stating that mourning is the process in which we detach self-energies from the beloved and prepare to service new relationships and activities, which has been a cornerstone of grief psychology. As pointed out by Freud, this process enables the bereaved individual to move on positively and begin a new phase of the life cycle, during which they may form new bonds and

become emotionally whole again (Hooyman et al., 2021). This theory was later expanded and developed by other psychologists who built the framework into a more complex conception of grief that considered its different phases and facets. Later, these models were developed based on Freud, which included aspects like the dynamic process of loss and restitutive coping processes with the help of reconstructions and the theory like the contemporary one, known as the Dual Process Model of Grief (Defoe & David, 2023). Altogether, these new and modern theories play an essential role in demonstrating the complexities of grief and the loss of mourning context, which discuss both aspects of detachment being vital for grieving and the other element of grieving being helpful to strengthen.

The Stage Models of Grief

The mid-20th century marked a significant turning point in the study of grief with the emergence of stage models, epitomized by Elizabeth Kübler-Ross's renowned five stages of grief: stages of grief and known as denial, anger, bargaining, depression, and acceptance (Mingo & Sharon, 2023). When conducting a literature review, it is essential to identify one work that has shed a great deal of insight on the subject matter; for this subject, that work is known as Kübler-Ross's model since it has brought order to this grieving, thus giving clinicians some order, form, and taxonomy with which to approach this grieving. When Kübler-Ross defined these various stages, she intended to emphasize that grieving is not a stagnant experience but rather a progression over time (Klerk & Mias, 2023, pp. 153-164). Her model clicked with clinicians and the general populace, giving them a veil of comfort where there was none, turning a disorganized and bewildering chaos into something they could try to understand. Furthermore, Kübler-Ross settled on the focus on how one had to 'work through' each stage, which, despite the grim tone and language of grief stages, implied a degree of agency and movement towards attaining acceptance.

Subsequent research and clinical practices have all raised questions about the simple stages presented in such stage theories as Kübler-Ross' model (Corr et al., 2020, pp. 61-67). It is for this reason that other people's models are said to hinder than trigger the mourning process since they are far from being comprehensive: those who developed the models under consideration argue that grief is much more than a sequence and that the 'stages' view is too mechanistic to capture the fundamental nature of mourning which may very quickly be pathological by these models (Bernau & John, 2022). However, the argument must be made that grief is not easy to fit into this type of model as people come up with various feelings and ways of functioning that may not easily fit into this type of format. However, these criticisms do not diminish the value Kübler-Ross offered to the bio-psycho-social model on grief for making a phenomenal beginning in mapping out a palliative approach that describes grieving as a succession of emotions that must be respected, recognized, and worked through. They provided the basis for current practice today in grief therapy as program developers try to create models that are more sensitive to person, environment, and process than were possible in earlier attempts at grief therapy, which is why they are essential for the current foundation of grief therapy.

Attachment Theory and Grief

The attachment theory forwarded by John Bowlby can be considered a groundbreaking approach to grieving, providing a rich understanding of the affective processes that underlie this form of mourning (Field, Nigel & Wogrin, 2021). Crying as an indicator of grief is not just a Psycho-social phenomenon based on loss, but an innate biological response instigated by the disruption of an attachment bond. Focusing on the biological roots of attachment, Bowlby shed light on the interaction between relationships and emotional regulation and demonstrated that grief is a normal and healthy mechanism. The principal contradiction in his theory's premise is that the

level of grieving is directly linked to the strength of the survivor's bond with the lost individual. Bowlby's propositions revealed the importance of the attached relationships for experiencing the loss and the true meaning of it, projecting the importance of the quality of these relationships.

In addition, there are arguments that Bowlby's theory has impacted the modern lacuna of grief therapy and changed the outlook of its direction concerning relationship aspects of bereavement (Robledo et al., 2022). Thus, by including the notions of nature and the history of the attachment bond in the set of relevant working tools, the contemporary therapist can offer more effective support to people who allow grief. While working with clients in bereaved states, therapists are guided by Bowlby to view the health of a client's grief through the lens of their relationships with others and cultural context, which in turn helps to assess the client's levels of attachment in developing coping strategies and emotional ways of functioning (Fitzgerald & Michael, 2021, pp. 119-119). This model of grief therapy stems from recognizing the interdependency of the emotional, psychological, and interpersonal realms, which can be targeted effectively with interventions per one's needs and histories. Thus, concerns underlying Bowlby's attachment theory remain vital for understanding the potential of more global, versatile, and sensitive approaches to grief and loss.

Contemporary Views and Integrative Models

In the last few decades, the evolution of grief therapy has been introduced, which has taken new directions and forms, including integrative and flexible models of treatment for grief (Kaplow et al., 2023). These modern concepts shift from the more defined and better-defined stages of grief present in prior times as the grieving process differs and is unique for each person. Instead of viewing the process of grieving as strictly stage-like and proceeding in the necessarily orderly fashion that most of the models we have seen suggest, these models acknowledge that, for each

individual, grieving is influenced by an almost limitless number of cultural, social, and personal factors. This change in cumulative grief has captured a more relativistic view, acknowledging that grief focuses on any conceivable type of loss.

Among these modern models, the Dual Process Model of Grief can be analyzed as an example as it describes the grieving process in detail (Fiore & Jennifer, 2021, pp.414-458). According to this model, individuals oscillate between two main coping processes: These two identified characteristics are known as loss-oriented and restoration-oriented. On the other hand, in the loss-oriented phase, the people deal with different feelings and the actuality of the loss and try to involve him or herself in various activities that are associated with the mourning of the dead person. In contrast, the restoration phase is characterized by finding a new normal in the absence of the deceased and negotiating new roles and functions in the bereaved individuals' lives (Giannini & Anthony, 2020). This intricate interplay of coping behaviors enables people to manage the complexities of mourning and the adaptive challenges of daily living. Naturally, the Dual Process Model posited in this paradigm asserts loss and restoration. However, both are vital aspects of grief in conflict, and grief therapy, therefore, should acknowledge both concepts.

Current Approaches to Grief Therapy

Diagnostic and Statistical Manual (DSM) Approach

The American Psychiatric Association's diagnostic and statistical manual is fundamental because it was launched to serve as a guide when diagnosing mental illnesses (American Psychiatric Association, 2020). But in its latest edition, the DSM provides detailed symptom lists for diagnosing grief-related conditions like major depressive disorder with persistent complex bereavement disorder. This inclusion can be seen as an attempt to categorize and map grief reactions people have within the disability model of mental health, thus offering clinicians clear-

cut criteria to identify and manage clients who may be experiencing complicated or prolonged grief. In diagnosing mental disorders, the DSM identifies the necessary steps to standardize the diagnosing process, thus eliminating the possibility of inconsistency in diagnosing.

Although grief symptomatology was included in the DSM, it has raised quite a lot of controversy in the field of psychology and psychiatry. Some critics have used the term ‘medical Trojan horse’ to argue that couching grief in the language of disorder has negative implications, including the medicalization of something that is a normal part of human life (Bonfini & Jayna, 2021). Loss is commonly defined as the adaptive response or reaction to grief, an interpersonal and cognitive process consisting of a broad concept with an emotional, cognitive, and behavioral component. It also makes grief easy to dismiss, and it potentially discounts the specifics of each case as it tries to force every grieving process into the neatly defined diagnosis that the DSM approach provides. In addition, the diagnostic criteria provided in the DSM can be insufficient to embrace all the bereavement outcomes that can cause problems of categorization or underdiagnoses of clients who are desperately experiencing their grief (Varinen & Alekski, 2023). As pointed out in the previous sections, the DSM is a valuable reference for clinicians in assessing mental health conditions. However, when we focus on grief-related disorders, the major issues have been discussed in detail that enclose the pros and cons of the application of DSM.

The DSM of grief therapy has remained a significant practice model in practicing clinicians due to their evidence on diagnosing and treating mental disorders (First et al., 2023, pp. 869-875). However, some have raised concerns, especially regarding the classification of grief-related disorders such as Major Depressive Disorder with Persistent Complex Bereavement Disorder. The establishing of specific parameters, the DSM effectively denies grief its independent status as a mental disorder, acknowledging it only when the time taken to grieve is more than what is standard

or if specific manifestations are observed (Morrison & James, 2023). The of these may include persistent mood of depression, guilt, or inability to let go after the loss. It could be argued that the idea behind creating these diagnostic criteria is to facilitate the identification of people who may require some form of symptomatic treatment. Still, the approach leads to the outright ideological medicalization of grief. It narrows the grief down to some plausible norms and does not understand that grief patterns are unique within people since every person is different.

Furthermore, the DSM approach neglects to consider the complexity of grief, which encompasses various aspects of the grieving process, including the psychosocial context, cultural and social background, and individual differences of the griever (Peak & Ashley, 2021). Hence, criticizing and pathologizing 'grief reactions' may be considered normal grief reactions when the criteria of time and specific symptoms are presented in the DSM. It can be detrimental for those grieving, especially since it may make people doubt the legitimacy of their feelings and delay help seeking out of fear they may be diagnosed with a mental disorder. There may also be other negative consequences associated with the diagnostic approach, such as the fact that while using it, the focus is no longer on providing comforting and supporting emotional care to grieving people but on trying to minimize the symptoms that the individuals demonstrate. Consequently, the call for a change in assessing grief-related disorders and a shift towards a more empathetic form of grief therapy that respects the complexities of the human grieving process has seen a more prominent spotlight in the field of psychology and counseling.

The controversies that still surround the DSM approach to grief have been tinging the field of psychology and counseling for quite some time (Lahey & Benjamin, 2021). The DSM, in fact, 'medicalizes' grief in its broad and unanalytical definition where new categories it formulates, such as Major Depressive Disorder with Persistent Complex Bereavement Disorder, effectively

turn grieving into a mental illness that will require professional interference. This approach fails to consider the nature of grief as being more diverse and complex, which they put into checking and trying to fit into specific diagnostic criteria. As a result, when people are going through the grieving process, these individuals may be diagnosed with a particular mental health disorder just because of the usual feelings of grief and struggle that come with losing a loved one.

In addition to this, the DSM has continued to pathologize grief, thus continuing to reinforce the medical model of thinking, thereby hiding the fact that grief should be a linear process of healing, with any digression from the process construed as abnormal or pathological (Ione & Adrienne, 2024, pp. 67-112). Lacking plausibility theory reduces the understanding of grief as an outcome of an interaction between various endogenous and exogenous factors, including cultural and individual factors, as well as the type of the losing relation (Wang et al., 2021, 476- 486). People who are not back on track, who take a little longer to grieve, or who display behaviors that are not typical of any average person grieving the loss of their loved ones may be forced to undergo some clinical procedures that may only worsen their conditions. The focus on grief, as presented by the DSM approach, means that instead of utilizing the concept to explain the site and source of strength in people, it becomes a pathological tool used to erase the possibility of personal transformation that comes with the process of mourning.

Specifically, the diagnostic framework of grief has been criticized, especially in the DSM, as being insufficient in capturing both the various manifestations of grief and the individual and environmental circumstances involved in those processes. In this respect, grief is highly individualistic and depends on many factors, such as cultural underpinnings, support and network, and the nature of the bereavement (Gryuk & Emilia, 2020). However, the DSM approach is usually a more conventional approach that sees it as a standardized procedure of diagnosing grief-related

disorders by prescribing certain sets of parameters and time restraints. This notion completely disregards the variables associated with grieving and can result in the misdiagnosis of normal grieving as complicated grieving. In addition, arising from this evidence, the medicalization of grief in this framework means that loss is constantly ill and not healthy, that is normal. The DSM framework runs the dangerous precedent of diagnosing certain forms of coping with grief as a mental pathology when what may simply be happening is that the person is going through a normal, healthy process of adaptation to the loss of a loved one.

Furthermore, the diagnostic criteria for grief therapy imply that grieving persons are distressed, thus aggravating their suffering through the prescription of ideal unfolding and duration of grief. Specifically, the DSM approach to describing grief reduces it to a disorder if it lasts beyond a particular time or when specific symptoms are present, such as worthlessness or suicidal thoughts (Reed et al., 2022, pp. 189-213). This may make the ones who are in severe emotional distress or have difficulty in coping with the loss of their dear ones feel as if they are flaking in their response or rewarding themselves to be silly. Also, it can make people avoid sharing their sorrow with their friends, families, or community or seek help from them since they might feel that they have a mental illness and need medical attention (Glorioso et al., 2020, pp. 245-256). As such, the very diagnostic framework cannot identify the range of grief and also potentially discourages a person from seeking out support, which is often vital in coping with grief or similar stressors.

The guidelines and framework for delivering grief therapy outlined in the DSM are diagnostic in approach, which only serves to perpetuate the prejudice that comes with mourning (Turner, Blocker & Sarah, 2023). After learning that one's grief reactions are not considered standard in comparison to those exhibited by other people or are not observed in appropriate time

frames, a person may experience feelings of low self-worth or even abnormality. Additionally, the failure of culture to acknowledge grief past a certain period also adds pressure on those mourning to either deny their feelings or act happy to conform to society's expectations (Eyetsemitan & Death, 2021). Such is common for individuals experiencing severe grief as they may feel abandoned or misjudged, would not seek help, or even want to go for therapy and later end up being associated with a mental illness. The stigma is worse in cultures or societies where emotional bereavement is not embraced, and the affected parties endure the pain and agony in secrecy, thus worsening their conditions.

Furthermore, they added that the noted tendency toward stigmatizing grief is not just about words but has potential consequences that can affect mental-health-related life trajectories and treatment results (Kokou-Kpolou et al., 2020, pp. 171-184). The current study was developed to examine how individuals' grief reactions impact their coping and whether people who avoid seeking professional help feel that their grief is pathological or if they should be able to get over it. This makes someone distant from those who can help come to terms with the loss, which only prolongs the suffering and increases the probability of developing severe mental problems like depression or anxiety (Fennel et al., 2021, p.553). Further, cultural beliefs regarding grief may interfere with the therapeutic process because the patients may assume that the therapists will not accept them if they reveal their grief. This may influence the success of therapy sessions and reduce the confidence that clients and therapists have in each other. In sum, the remaining stigmatization of the diagnostic approach to grief therapy does not only increase the pain of suffering individuals but also fosters major, and at times insurmountable, barriers to wishing for adequate assistance and care.

Critique of the Diagnostic Approach to Grief

Pathologizing Normal Grief Reactions

Another valid source of concern with the diagnostic approach to grief is the darkness such an approach must create when it is all about ordinary, banal, and rightful human grief responses (Neimeyer & Robert, 2021). Saying that the limitation of this approach is the lack of recognition of the natural differences in grieving keenly, which is due to high adherence to the DSM-5 to include rigid timeframes and symptom counts for classifying PGD and other grief-related disorders. Bereavement is unique and affected by numerous factors, including the loss's nature, the mourner's bond with the departed, and cultural and individual factors (Connor & Frances, 2020, pp. 43-46). The criteria for the diagnostic approach do not allow for these differences, which may lead to the understanding of normal grief reactions as pathological.

This continues to hurt anyone who is grieving and makes me wonder about the role of medicine when it comes to grief. People who, for instance, fail to fit the diagnostic criteria may be left feeling left out, looked down upon, or discriminated against because their natural process of mourning is termed a mental disorder. This misinterpretation not only superimposes a new layer of suffering unrelated to grief but can also make a person doubt whether their supposed grief is warranted (Wordsworth & Kat, 2023). There are still cultural and societal expectations regarding how one would grieve or heal. This hampers the grieving process since society imposes a time to grieve that is unhealthy for everyone. This highlights the importance of a more personalized approach that respects how individuals experience and respond to mourning.

Inadequate Cultural Considerations

A cultural cognate for grief often implies that culture is a remnant or overlay of grief rather than an influencing factor in mourning. Cultures play a crucial role in someone's grieving process

because culture dictates how individuals grieve (Tateo & Luca, 2023, pp. 411-433). Conversely, these diagnostic criteria are inadequate in encompassing these variations, thus causing the risk of complicating the assessment or overlooking grief reactions. This is especially vices for people of color or non-western or the marginalized since they always exhibit their grief in a different way that may not meet the set standard known in hospitals (Eyetsemitan & Frank). Thus, such people can be stigmatized for a grief-related disorder, or their subjective grief can be disregarded or poorly understood.

The first argument is that a lack of cultural awareness and cultural competence in diagnosing grief may lead to scant opportunities for culturally sensitive grief support and interventions. Losing loved ones is painful enough; thereby, cultural insensitivity makes suffering continue, and patients do not get the right kind of support they need as they mourn their loved ones. Moreover, this void only expands the physical and emotional loneliness and the feeling of being an outcast of the grieving people because their forms of mourning are not recognized and embraced in clinical psychology (Dibekulu et al., 2024, p.100402). It is crucial to address all these cultures to work towards compiling a better grief therapy that acknowledges and embraces the different cultures in accepting and honoring diverse grieving mechanisms.

Overemphasis on Symptomatology

The criteria for diagnosing grief-related disorders are usually focused on specific manifestations that suggest that loss is still felt, for example, profound feelings of sadness, guilt, or the occurrence of obsessions related to the deceased individual (Simon et al., 2020, p. 9-16). These symptoms are parts of the grieving process; however, excluding the rest of the aspects and painting the grieving process only in these colors is inadequate. These risks limit grief as a subject with only the symptoms that must be addressed rather than as a complex process unique to the

individual. It may lead to some interventions that focus on minimizing the intensity of grief, which may be unhelpful since grief encompasses other methods, including the need to find a new meaning in life, effects on relationships, and philosophical questions.

As a result, diagnostic focus on the symptoms can skew their view of grief and fail to consider other psychological factors (Boelen, Paul & Lenferink, 2022, pp. 667- 674). It is implied that the focus on the purposeful work for meaning making and coming to terms with the loss as part of the grieving process might be overshadowed by the effort to address more apparent symptoms. Since this can lead to a lack of focus on personal traits, the therapeutic model can lack touch with individual grief. Furthermore, understanding and implementing the support and support seeking in interpersonal relationships and dealing with questions of meaning and purpose in life that emerge after a bereavement might go unnoticed (Gilbert et al., 2021, p.405). As a result, there is a reductionist approach to the analysis of symptomatology, which does not allow for the proper handling and helping of the bereaved and offers little chance of giving complete and empathetic care that would better embody the complexity of grief.

Ignoring Grief as a Transformative Process

One major criticism leveled towards the diagnostic model of grief is that this model does not acknowledge grief as a process of healing that has the potential to produce positive changes in the person going through it. Several distinct models have been proposed that conceptualize grief more in a positive way than simply as an illness that needs to be treated or managed in some way or another and that focus on the positive potential for the creation of post-traumatic growth, as well as rediscovery of the self and growth throughout this process (Kochen et al., 2020). This having-said-that perspective recognizes that, although grieving is a painful and challenging experience, it

can also be a healing and growth-inducing process in which those mourning undergoes profound transformations and discover new purposes.

Through the process of carrying out diagnosis, the growth opportunities that these grief reactions offer are sidetracked. Such categorization is likely to stifle grief and impose medical model-based interventions on the bereaved with no regard for the sociopolitical, psychological, and spiritual plans that need to be developed to support grieving individuals (Sutton & Barbara, 2020). This might hinder the normal developmental process required in seeking positive change after a loss since it is associated with a specific loss. On the other hand, if grief therapy were to embrace what has been said and expand its scope, people would be assisted in their grieving process while learning to use their coping mechanisms; this would lead to a better quality of life after the death of someone close.

Limited Evidence Base and Reliability

These critics, therefore, argue that empirical data underlying the DSM diagnostic criteria for grief-related disorders, including the criteria for PGD, are questionable, and the requirements fail to adequately demarcate normal and pathological grief responses (Sarli & Carina, 2021). Due to the lack of adequate evidence validating the effectiveness of the diagnostic tools used in assessing grief, there is more emphasis placed on the culture and diversity aspects of grief experiences. Therefore, this critique provides an analysis of the validity of the routine use of specific diagnostic labels in the diagnosis of grief, based on its philosophical and subjective nature, in a bid to question the relevance of the frameworks in guiding the development of treatment plans. Therefore, there is an increased understanding of the need to search for a different perspective that is far more complex and less limiting, that captures the variations and realities of grief and the experience of every person mourning the loss.

Critiques about the lack of feasibility of such a diagnostic approach to grief mirror broader discussions on the medicalization and pathologization of experiences and states in people (Hansen & Hillerup, 2022). In this way, grief has been medicalized, or rather, pathologized, because, by formulating it as a list of specific signs and symptoms with certain criteria that have to be met, it is likely to minimize and even fail to recognize the variability of the psychological, social, and cultural processes influence grieving. Having considered some of the latest attitudes and opinions concerning the concept and experience of grief, there is a growing concern for changing approaches that focus on the idea that grief is therapeutic, constructive, and constructive morality central to understanding the human person and the general existential significance. This shifting of the diagnostic lens in the definition of grief not only disrupts psychosocial expectations in grieving people but also provides more opportunities for intervention-sensitive healing and support systems for mourners.

The Human Experience of Grief: A Phenomenological Approach

Emphasis on Subjective Experience

Phenomenology as a philosophical approach and qualitative research method is interested in what and how people experience or give meaning to phenomena (Urcia & Aldrich, 2021). In the context of grief, they indicate that the assessment and treatment process should focus on subjectivity or how people understand and make sense of their bereavement experiences. When studying grief through the lens of the first-person narrative, researchers mirror the complexity of grief, accepting that grief is not a monolithic phenomenon. This methodological orientation recognizes the variety of mourners and how they grieve and assumes that the personalized path of grief is acceptable (Gill & Michael, 2020, pp.73-94). From this perspective, it is far easier to

understand grief in its purist sense while acknowledging that grieving is not a uniform process but one laden with subtleties and differences.

In other words, phenomenology encourages the researcher to put on a mourner's sandals and lose themselves in the experience of grief (Cadavid & Anita, 2022, pp. 1-150). This contrasts with forcing onto people's lives, state of being, or dysfunction some fixed a priori concepts such as DSM's classifications. In understanding that one's subjective truth is valid and identifying with the complexities of generative loss, researchers gain insight into how grief defines people. Lastly, focusing on one's experience in phenomenological research helps enhance our understanding of grief.

Exploration of Meaning-Making Processes

Phenomenological analysis explores the complex processes that occur in people when they experience constructing meanings at a loss (Manen & Max, 2023). Fundamentally, this search investigates the questions concerning the meaning of life, situating itself within the existential dilemmas that emerge from loss and exploring the confrontation with meaning crises and the questioning of values. This way, scholars intend to explain the profound impacts of grief in the context of existential aspects of human lives and the roles we embrace. In an endeavor to map the richly layered existential panorama of grief-ended lives, scholars endeavor to trace the complex processes and subtleties of grief as it implicates the thematic construction of individual identity and cosmological perspective at profound existential levels, which is inherent in the profound disruption of such fundamental life structures and processes.

Consequently, from a phenomenological perspective, grief is a fascinating journey through the human mind that provides glimpses of how meaning-laden worlds are built in the face of adversity (Hannush & James, 2021). This line of research analysis rises beyond simply

observation; it calls for deep self-analysis and thinking to philosophize. Such is the grandeur of existential accumulation, which shows scholars how to reason effectively when the world ceases to make sense and sail through the endless storms of grief in the vast ocean of human experience. In this manner, this research seeks to study further the complexities of grieving and shed more light on the real essence of meaning reconstruction pursuit in the mourning process.

Recognition of Ambiguity and Contradiction

One particularly cherished element of the phenomenological approach is the unresolved tension and paradox at the heart of grieving (Jayasundara & Nadeeshani, 2023). Many people who have essential assets either through death, loss of job, or any other circumstances that result in them experiencing what they don't wish in life may, at times, go through many emotions that may not easily be categorized. This is illustrated by the presence of what appear to be opposites and seems to be a form of grief where happiness that comes with acceptance is found hand in hand with loss and the desire to go back, or a feeling of sadness that is coupled with a sense of relief in that the worse may be over. Through phenomenology, these bipolar experiences are situated as snapshots of the grieving process and not as impediments to it (Wierzbinska & Eliza, 2023). Due to this, phenomenological inquiry tends to blur the clear lines drawn by the more traditional psychological models of grief and acknowledges the ambiguity of the grieving process.

The phenomenological approach has benefited researchers because it allows them to look more deeply into how various emotions influence one another and the cognitive aspect of the grieving person (Nin & Rafis, 2023). Instead of attempting to reconcile such contradictions, the phenomenological approach encourages researchers to investigate these aspects of the experiment further and consider their implications concerning the individual's lived experience. This simulation attests to the flexibility of grief interactively and gives an understanding of grief to

portray loss dynamically. As such, phenomenological research can elicit a more accurate and compassionate understanding of the challenging and complex grieving process and reveal areas where this or that participant may need support to heal from the loss they have experienced.

Attention to Temporality

Since phenomenology encompasses the temporal element as part thereof, it can effectively capture the dynamics of grief. Hearley appreciates one concept that grief is not a destination but a process that occurs over time. This recognition includes understanding that grief is not a progressive linearity in which intensity or relevance increases and then decreases as people go through different stages of grieving (Ratcliffe & Matthew, 2023, pp. 1067-1086). By exploring how grief moves over time, researchers could learn the complexity of the grieving process. It allows them to look at how humans change over time, not just with an eye on the processes, cycles, or stages of grief, but also with a sense of how people cope, rebound, and transform within that process.

Temporality, too, gives grief a central place, as phenomenology emphasizes the need to pay attention to how the past, present, and future intertwine to shape the experience of grief. It postures itself to know how memories play in the ongoing pre-loss state and grieving at the current moment and how anticipated grief can interfere with or assist expectations of loss and preparing for the inevitable future (Pang & Joanna). In this way, a more integrated approach can be taken where researchers and therapists analyze the grieving process and recognize that there are many aspects to the process and that individuals' reactions to loss are diverse and multi-layered. This rich perspective helps clinicians and caregivers directly support the grieving person better because it looks at grief not as a state but as a changing and evolving process.

Integration of Personal Narrative

In this context, adopting personal narratives as an avenue for quantifying experiences in phenomenological research helps ground the poignant subjective complexities of grieving. When studying loss narratives and analyzing people's subjective experiences, researchers can investigate the multifaceted phenomena of grief and its psychological and social aspects (Koster, Allan & Fernandez, 2023, pp. 149-169). These tales paint a complex picture of grieving, thus capturing the complex and often unique way people go through grief. Through such listening, their role is to gain a more profound and rich appreciation of people's grief beyond the binary classification, often employed while acknowledging how complex grieving processes are. Also, a personal narrative strategy is valuable information as individuals' narratives allow researchers to study the peculiarities of the contexts that influence grief. The value given to the context, culture, and personal experiences demonstrates the importance of adopting contextual and cultural analysis in understanding the different responses to loss and formulating a culturally sensitive approach in grief research and therapy.

Including the first-person testimonials about the loss in phenomenological analysis of grief not only provides deeper insight into the particulars of a particular case but also emphasizes the social aspect of the grieving process (Ratcliffe et al., 2023). Thus, the narrative of one counts on the others in a way designed to move beyond the self, as well as its understanding of personal relationships and social expectations. These narratives underscore the significance of ensuring social connectedness and participation in communal observances, asserting that the loss of loved ones is coexistence with recognizing how the collective mourns in culturally appropriate ways, indicating that individual grief sits firmly within a social frame. Moreover, incorporating personal stories offers hope to suffering people and enables them to stand up for their experiences so their

voices are heard. In sum, personal stories benefit phenomenological research and support and treatment of individuals experiencing grief by these means: First, personal stories help people understand the raw reality of grief or any other phenomenon and how people deal with it.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This research design selected for this study on grief as a human experience and the call for a different approach to grief therapy is well planned to capture the research questions while being methodologically sound. Recognizing that the research falls into the qualitative territory and focuses on the participant's subjective experiences of the phenomenon of interest, a phenomenological research approach is used. Phenomenology aims at describing the nature of experience by paying attention to the subjectively given meaning of the experience (Williams & Heath, 2021, pp. 366-385). This aligns with the study's principal purpose: spotlighting grief as a normal part of the human experience while documenting how people perceive and manage their grief.

To achieve the research objectives, semi-structured interviews are conducted with two distinct groups of participants: people who faced significant breaks in their lives and therapists who specialize in grief therapy. The semi-structured interviews used in the study permit the structure of questions in investigations but also can explore deeper themes about grief as well as the therapeutic operations that are considered vital (Paredes et al., 2021, p. 11393). The participants are recruited using purposive sampling to represent the diverse ranges of age, gender, cultural background, and their level of close relationship with the deceased. This allows the researcher to get diverse outlooks and appraisals that enrich the data gathered and collected, making coverage more expansive and comprehensive.

The semi-structured interviews are based on predetermined questions that aim to allow the respondents to provide comprehensive answers and branch off by describing their experiences of grief and the emotions it triggers. The questions can address the subject's losses, how they deal

with grief, the role of health care providers in their case, and the professional and individual characteristics of modern grieving treatment models. Through such open-ended interviews, the participants can share much about the nature of grief that might otherwise go unexplored if a standardized set of questions were used and discussed with clinicians.

However, data collection is done sensitively and ethically, bearing in mind the state of mood of the participant and the general well-being of the participants as they speak about their experiences of loss. Participants are made to understand the purpose, process, risks, and benefits of the study, and consent is sought from them while ensuring their identity and data remain unknown to the outsider (Adikaram et al., 2022, pp. 376-395). This helps to ensure that participants are comfortable with participating in the study and are informed that they are free to withdraw from the study at any time without any repercussions. Furthermore, the researcher takes a reflexivity perspective to the entire data collection and analysis process, whereby the researcher cannot help but impart their personal bias and assumptions in the research process but makes a conscious effort to reduce their impact on the study.

After all the interviews, the data is written down in a Word document and translated into an exact written language, and then content analysis is done. Thematic analysis is a versatile and organized approach to identifying, analyzing, and describing patterns (themes) within the data collected via qualitative research (Ozuem et al., 2022, pp.143-157). It can be defined as the coding of the data, the classification of the results, and the interpretation of familiar ideas or patterns. The categorization is cyclical and looped, with the researcher continually going up and down the data to ensure that each potential perspective has been discussed concerning the themes under consideration. In this way, the specific approach increases the researcher's understanding of the

participants' experience of grief and how the current grief therapy paradigm is perceived or received.

In conclusion, the research design used in this study is most appropriate for the type of research questions posed and where the study aims to gain insight into grief as a human process. Qualitative information collection procedures like semi-structured interviews and thematic analysis allow the study to understand the richness and intensity of grief (Downar et al., 2020, pp. 685-693). They may help enhance grief therapy practices more effectively. By practicing ethical consideration and a methodological approach to the study, the findings are guaranteed to be credible and relevant.

Participants

The method utilized in this study is consistent with the principles of qualitative research to understand the complexity of loss and the variability of the participants' experiences and explore the practitioners' contribution to grief therapy. One of the present study's challenges is identifying participants who will offer meaningful results. It is noted that purposive sampling will be used to market participants because this method helps to select people who can provide valuable and meaningful data on the discussed topic (Campbell et al., 2020, pp. 652-661). Participants for the study will be sampled from bereaved individuals, and only those who have lost a loved one within the last two years shall be included in the analysis because the impact of grief is fresh. They should be willing to be interviewed. In addition to using the general call for participants, expert end-of-life practitioners such as psychologists, counselors, and social workers will be sourced based on their published work and interventions in grief therapy.

As for the sampling, different techniques will be used, namely advertising on supporters' bereavement groups and pages, social media, and LinkedIn. All the possible participants will be

informed of the research, its aim, methods, benefits, and potential drawbacks. All participants will sign consent to participate in the study to establish that they comprehend the aims and purposes of the research and their rights as members of the research. Participants will also be informed about the voluntary nature of the response to the study questions and the anonymity of the responses. Also, it will be explained to them that they have the right to withdraw from the study at any time without reason.

The primary source of data collection will entail semi-structured interviews conducted face-to-face or through technological means, namely video conferencing. Semi-structured Interviews can be beneficial in allowing an opportunity to probe deeper into participants' experiences while simultaneously having the option to cope with emerging themes and subthemes (Cossart et al., 2022, pp. 887-898). To fully explore the participant's individual grief experiences, strengths, and limitations of the current models of grief therapy to health professionals and client's understanding, the following interview questions will be asked: Follow-up questions will be applied in a research study to facilitate further explanations on the responses and more focus on specific fields.

Both participants will be asked permission to record the interviews on an audio device to ensure a true spoken copy of the interviews for later transcription for the analysis. Transcription is vital for adherence with participant responses and provides a better view of the data collected. Furthermore, research interviews may be complemented with participant observation or document analysis, if necessary and if the appropriate research material is available. Participant observation includes the observer actively engaging the setting and immersing him or herself in learning grief-related interactions of people in natural or genuine contexts such as support groups or therapy

sessions. Content analysis entails analyzing the various written or visual data on grief therapy, including the treatment manuals, articles, or notes.

According to the data analysis plan, data analysis will be done thematically, where the researcher will be patterned depending on themes, patterns, and meaning. This will be followed by familiarization, where the researcher will read and even listen to the interview transcripts numerous times. Subsequently, first-order codes are developed to categorize other concepts or themes in the data that have emerged from the preliminary analysis. These codes will then be grouped into more general categories or subthemes through coding and classification. These themes will be discussed in detail and reviewed via successive analysis cycles to ensure they capture all the diversification and complexity of the data collected. In the final step, findings will be discussed in connection to the research questions and prior findings to offer information on grieving and the practice of grief therapy.

Details of the study and the survey results will be reported in detail and in a manner that encompasses detailed descriptions of quotes from the participants involved in the study. The findings will also be grouped categorically, thus categorizing the major categories and their respective subcategories identified during the analysis of the raw data. Conclusion of the study, the findings for theory, research, and practice would be presented, limitations of this study would also be pointed out, and recommendations would be deemed correct for further studies. With a well-defined strategy and analysis of the data gained from interviews, this research seeks to help improve grief therapy by providing insight into the complexity of this aspect of human existence.

Data Collection Methods

While considering the method in this dissertation, it was essential to choose efficient data collection methods to address the heterogeneity of grief experiences and the differing views of mental health. Considering that the study focused on processing grief, which cannot be easily quantified, and given that grief is multifaceted and may have different manifestations, it was thought that a qualitative paradigm would be most appropriate for this study (Woodworth et al., 2023, pp. 562-577). Using the qualitative view is easier and more effective in understanding people's experiences than the quantitative view, which is often rigid and does not capture different people's experiences. Quantitative data used in this study were collected from interviews with people who have experienced significant loss and clinicians in grief counseling.

Participants were identified through purposive sampling, where the primary criterion was that they had been involved with grief or grief therapy. The inclusion criterion centered on the type of sample needed, a wide range of ages, male and female participants, different cultures, and different statuses of the corpse, ensuring the method captured as many views as possible. Semi-structured interviews were selected to carry out the process with the possibility of a more natural flow of conversation, allowing the participants to respond to questions most comfortably and follow their referring pace (Bihu & Reuben, 2020). The interview process was structured and formal to ensure that all relevant issues regarding grief were covered; questions tapped into personal strategies for handling grief, past involvement in therapy, and the Participants' general impression of the diagnostic process.

To avoid any ethical challenges in the conduct of the study, consent to participate was sought and signed by all the participants before the interviews. All the participants were given comprehensive information on the research goals and objectives, methodology, and participants'

rights and risks involved in the study. All the participants were informed of anonymity and that they were free to pull out of the study at any time. Furthermore, precautions were made to establish ways of limiting all the potential adverse effects that might come about due to discussing some of the issues that are sensitive and may cause complications to grief. If the participant felt too stressed, they were free to take a break or terminate the interview process; available support counseling services were given to them.

The interviews were conducted in a quiet and comfortable environment to not force participants into a particular opinion or zone of discomfort. The interviewer followed the narrative principles and adopted an empathetic, non-judgmental approach, focusing on listening and affirming every participant's lived experience (McKenzie & Blake, 2023). The respondents were asked consecutive questions, encouraging them to provide a deeper insight into their current positions and minimize any vagueness that characterized their replies. The interviews were conducted with the participants' approval, who subsequently agreed to have the audio recorded to transcribe them, hence generating a means of data analysis.

Interviews with subjects, which include each of the five stages of grief, were also supplemented with interviews with practitioners of grief therapy. These practitioners were chosen because the population under study is one of the most helpless groups of people who have lost someone dear to them, and it was deemed essential that the collected information be based on practical experience and professional ethics. To gather more data on current practice in delivering grief therapy, the practitioner interviews posed questions on the utilization of DSM diagnostic criteria and the problems with addressing grief as a mental disorder (Kobak et al., 2023). Like in the interviews with grieving persons, the interviews with the practitioners were also semi-structured, and the ethical issues involved were carefully observed.

Credibility measures were taken during the data collection to establish the authenticity of the results. This entailed self-observation while embracing the role of the researcher, hence practically analyzing the role of the researcher as a method of data interference. Triangulation was also used by comparing the results of different kinds of data from interviews with both the bereaved and practitioners, and research focused on grief therapy was available in the literature (Willi et al., 2024, p.59). This also opened an opportunity to explain and elaborate on some of the results and views presented to build credibility for the study. Last, member checking was carried out by presenting emerging findings to the participants and allowing them to cross-check the results to establish the credibility of the obtained data.

In general, the methods used for data collection in this study were chosen in a way that will provide the most diverse and insightful views on grief and its therapies. This study sought to better understand the grief process by interviewing people who had grieved or lost loved ones and grief practitioners to get an insight into the issue's intricacies and offer input for refining the grief therapy. Since this study followed ethical standards and utilized a research method that complies with the necessary standards, it is believed that the data obtained can significantly contribute to developing knowledge in this study area.

Data Analysis Procedure

The first step in analyzing the gathered data included the initial contact with the data collected during the interviews. This involved listening to tapes, taking transcripts of all the interviews with Word and copying the data into Word, getting a total feel of all uncovered. Thus, during this phase, notes were taken regarding some first impressions about participants, notes of resolved conflicts, participation of the observer, any observation about participants that seemed exciting or unusual, and any possible pattern regarding the conflict that can be found. This

approach aimed to get a working feel for the information and look for familiar or perhaps emergent themes or topics for analysis for the next study phase.

Subsequently, the conceptual developer proposed generating the first codes upon getting familiar with the data. This included separating and labeling the data flexibly in addressing the research questions, study goals, and objectives. In this research, the code was developed based on the appeal of the theme extracted from the participant interviews and their experiences, the importance of grief, and the processes related to it. Moreover, some codes utilized prior knowledge from the literature or knowledge repositories, while other codes were inductively developed based on trends and patterns in the data patterning process (Riazi et al., 2023, pp. 25-47). By using an iterative coding process, it was possible always to get more than one option reviewed, thus improving the coding and overall analysis until all information was correctly classified.

After the first coding of the data slice, the next step was to conduct a systematic search for themes. This entailed condensing the coded data into analytic categories and grouping these categories in a way that would adequately answer the research question. To achieve broad domain coverage, themes were judged in light of how often they occurred, their relation to the research questions, and the ability to shed light on numerous aspects of the dataset. By employing the constant comparison method, the obtained data segments underwent a comprehensive comparison and categorization process to capture similarities and variations in and between participants and interviews. This method made it possible for me to pinpoint leading patterns and encapsulate principal and relevant social aspects regarding grief and its handling from the participants' standpoint.

After the first topic selection, the consecutive phase of data analysis is aimed at reconsidering and refining the topic. Refinement means they analyze and discuss necessary steps

while examining each theme to reach sensible continuity and consistency besides their relationship to the research questions and objectives (Coker & David, 2022). These themes were finally developed by analyzing and interpreting the data collected and considering the broader contexts, semantics, and qualitative differences within the data. This process of step-by-step coding and reflecting on what we have found helped to uncover subtler or more intricate patterns that were possibly overlooked previously. They also enabled the inclusion of opposites or paradoxical views in case they were missed by the other researchers in the study, thereby providing textual and valid results.

After the theme was identified, the last process, known as the operationalization process, involved identifying and labeling the themes. This involved developing summary descriptions of the main qualities of the themes, which encapsulated the content in a simple yet informative manner. Themes were determined from each concept, idea, or phenomenon and were named descriptively. Pre-continentals were made to ensure that the identified themes agreed with the participants' experiences in understanding grief and its management and were not artificially induced. In the final thematic analysis report, all the themes were arranged in a sequential and logical format that is easy to follow and strictly accompanied by literature-backed quotes from the data.

During data analysis, various strategies were applied to improve the rigor and reliability of the analysis results. These included a comprehensive record of all analytical decisions and processes, peer debriefing and member checks of the interpretations of the data, and reflexivity exercises to scrutinize the researchers' biases, assumptions, and beliefs (Coleman & Phil, 2022, pp. 2041- 2045). This study employed strict data analysis processes to come up with accurate, credible, and substantive findings and conclusions concerning grieving and the nature of healing

and help for the grieving, in the hope of expanding the knowledge concerning grief therapy and the improved formulation of further compassionate therapeutic solutions for grieving individuals.

Ethical Considerations

In this study, profound ethical issues will be an essential item to be addressed since the research involves human participants and is focused on a sensitive domain, namely grief and bereavement. Before conducting the research, permission was sought from the relevant IRB to make sure that the study was done under cognizance of all the ethical rules set forth (Rentcome & Jessica, 2022). Hence, participants were asked for their written consent before engaging in any activity within the study to explain the study's risks and benefits to them. Thus, participants were informed of the voluntary nature of the study, anonymity, and the option to withdraw at any time. All the participants were asked to sign the written consent form, and before conducting the interview, they were verbally invited to participate in the study.

Organized risk minimization was maintained throughout the research when selecting participants and addressing the participants' rights and information privacy. Recordings and written interviews, field notes, and transcriptions were safeguarded and were available for viewing only by the research team. The participants were given aliases for any reports or presentations from the data collected in this study. Like participants' identification, anonymity and neutralization procedures were utilized throughout data analysis and reporting to ensure participants' information was not revealed to the public. Furthermore, participants were made aware of the possible harm that may befall them while participating in the study, including emotional loss or discomfort resulting from the interviews. Some measures were implemented to assist and link any participant who might be stressed during or after the interviews to a counselor.

Culture was given due consideration throughout the research process, potentially increasing the cultural sensitivity of the research (Joseph et al., 2021). Some attempts were made to ensure that participants were selected in a way that ensured they came from different cultural, religious, and belief backgrounds and experienced loss in various manners. The cultural competence training was made available to the researchers to ensure they gained insight into cultural diversity regarding grieving and mourning. Interview questions were standardized based on cultural norms and end views, meaning that questions that were posed related well to the cultural values of the respondents. The research was interdisciplinary, not imposing researchers' opinions on the participants but respecting their cultural beliefs and experiences. Cultural sensitivity was observed throughout the research process, and the participants' cultural values and standards were considered while addressing the crucial task of providing the participants' voices and perspectives.

The following measures were implemented to avoid compromising the research relationship by having the research team call the shots. The researchers started the experiment by cordially presenting the participants to one another and stating their fields of specialization. To achieve these objectives, the participants could contribute to the study without feeling humiliated or punished for their constructive or negative inputs. Ethical issues that were highlighted were ensuring participants were assured that the researchers focused solely on them, both in doing and not doing, did not negatively evaluate their behavior and that there was a shared interaction throughout the research study (Sutrop, Margit & Louk, 2020, pp. 213-232). Thus, the self-organization of participants and their self-direction were valued and safeguarded during the whole recruitment period and the conduct of the research study.

Free access to information or the use of best practices was considered critical value during the research. Concerning the subjects, they provided their informed consent about the aim, procedures, and report on the investigation. To ensure that the participants offered voluntary consent, methods were also provided and followed that would help the participants understand the study in precise forms and the role and influence of the participant. Before the survey, participants were allowed to get clarification on any aspects of the study that they found confusing and raise any issues that could make them unwilling to participate. To achieve this, researchers shared their position and affiliation to organizations and their reasons for conducting the study, making the participants comfortable around them. The study's results were shared with the participants early in the process so they could check whether the interpretations were accurate and relevant. As much as this study was conducted, we observed ethical considerations to safeguard individuals' rights, dignity, and welfare and ensure that the research process was valid and reliable.

RESULTS

Demographic Information of Participants

Age Distribution

The age distribution used in this study provides an adequate understanding of the participant's general characteristics that help judge potential differences that different stages of development may bring about (Chuey et al., 2021). If one can describe the age range, it becomes easier to establish varying patterns in how different ages approach and deal with grief. However, this chapter does not only reveal the differences but also the similarities in survival techniques that enlighten the agnostic and age-specific aspects of grieving. Framed through this view, the study intends to identify how age affects grieving to reveal distinct approaches to coping with grief in different stages of life.

Knowledge of age distribution among participants is of tremendous importance concerning the issue of how and to what extent one can provide grief support interventions to respond to participants' needs, depending on their age (Falk et al., 2022, pp.233-244). Data analysis separates the participants by different age groups to identify differences related to age in coping style and help-seeking. Further, it aims to establish any barriers unique to a particular age group that might call for special focus or support. In conclusion, this discussion is necessary for offering age-responsive child bereavement support to tailor interventions depending on an individual's age and indicating the need for more detailed qualifications for grief support based on developmental stages.

Gender Representation

This study also seeks to establish a proportionate distribution of gender participants to gain a differential understanding of gendered experiences of grief and bereavement. From the gender distribution, the study will seek to understand differences in psychological coping styles and support systems and help search for behaviors of men and women when encountering loss (Islam et al., 2022, p.102431). Awareness of such differences may help reveal how a particular culture and masculinity/femininity affect mourning. In addition, when considering gender regarding loss, there exist research possibilities to discover potential differences in the recognition and manifestation of the grieving process, as well as potential gender-based barriers to the receipt of support services.

It is important to bring gender concerns into the study of grief and in the development of grief therapy, as this discussion of gender representation makes a significant addition to the understanding of grief (Dodd et al., 2022, pp. 473-484). Therefore, appreciation of and concern for gender sensitivity that comes with acknowledging gender-specific concerns will allow clinicians to design acceptable intercession strategies and programs that will help to cater to the differentiated needs of bereaved individuals. Furthermore, it can help raise awareness and support the cause for gender-sensitive practices in handling societal grief, emphasizing gender norms. In this section, the author highlights gender and grief with accentuation and major focalization on the fact that gender is and must be taken as a variable of critical importance within the assessment of grief as storage.

Relationship to the Deceased

Among the connections explored in the segment on the relationship to the deceased, the study provides a detailed portrayal of multiple strands of affiliations embraced by the participants. From close kinship ties as spouses, parents, children, and siblings to less intimate circles of friends or other relatives, this section seeks to clarify various aspects of relationship gloom experiences (Pitrone & Michael, 2020). More importantly, the study investigates the extent of such emotional bonds and, thus, their effects on people's mourning experiences. By saying 'yes' to this exploration, one begins to gain a more intricate insight into the nature of grief-related reactions and how the level of intimacy and bond in interpersonal relationships may affect them.

Understanding the general participation indicates that the participants had conflicting emotions and sentiments that ranged from grief and anguish to joy and humor in remembering the deceased. This section focuses on the relationship quality's interdependency and the benefits stemming from grief responses while practicing palliative care, as described by Lengelle & Reinekke (2021). It is designed to determine how variables like closeness, bond, and dependency on those one uses to deal with the loss and their well-being. In identifying these dynamics, this study will seek to identify the diversity of roles and multiple interwoven tracks where people are likely to be as they go through grief.

In addition, it also enables one to be more informed about the nature of the bereaved's relationship with the deceased, which is integral in ascertaining the kind of assistance required by the bereaved person. Unlike the previous sections where the focus was on the mechanics of grieving and its manifestations, this part focuses on the importance of various relationships to the grieving process. Also, it defines the contacts and resources people use to manage grief. It also provides an understanding of the socio-matrix in grief, the different types of grief interventions,

and the specific support needs of the griever. Thus, this concept explains the intense care required depending on the particular grief experienced by the individual. This research is expected to facilitate an understanding of grief and support in later life and make positive changes to bereavement support activities, not only in the sample area but also across the healthcare system, to implement higher standards of care for grievers.

Cultural Background

Extending the concern to participants' cultural context is critical since many experiences might be found among the selected subjects. In this examination, it is possible to analyze the topics connected to culture, ethnicity, race, religion, and nationality. By considering these points, this study should be able to shed light on how people from different cultures grieve. The data obtained highlighted the importance of cultural orientation as a belief system that determines death culture, grieving customs, or practices related to mourning specifically, underlining the significance of cultural sensitivity in works devoted to grief.

Understanding insecure cultural differences helps healthcare providers be sensitive and develop appropriate approaches toward mourners. This section will further explore how gender and other aspects of culture shape people's expectations and ways of responding to mourning and loss (Silverman et al., 2021, pp. 1-8). The fulfillment of cultural expectations may influence how grief is communicated, recognized, or responded to and the help that a grieving person seeks. Knowledge of these dynamics may contribute towards more empathic and culturally appropriate practices in grief therapy, especially for individuals in different cultures.

Additionally, expanding the cultural focus in bereavement studies benefits the diverse groups described above and the discourse on cultural responsiveness and equity within mental health care. Therefore, this section draws attention to the nature of culture and grief by discussing

the intricacies of people's experiences to counter the top-down Hegemonic culture grief narratives that may erase or exclude certain cultural groups (Atas & Ahmet, 2023). It stresses the best practice of cultural sensitivity in grief therapy, where everyone's culture, regardless of culture, is honored.

Duration of Grief

This research, therefore, seeks to establish how long participants grieve after burying their loved ones in a bid to find out the temporal factors of grief. It will incorporate the assessment of the exact time that a person or a set of people has been grieving and how long it will take for such grief to be resolved concerning the persons' present emotional statuses and their ability to cope with issues affecting them. Through investigation of the time taken within grieving, properties of this process can be revealed, such as its phases, changes, and possible consequences on people's well-being (Testoni et al., 2020, p.110). This review shall provide a better perspective into the potential nature of change in grief and factors that may be directly linked to grief duration and possibly the severity of the grief process.

Further, studying the time factor of grief is vital to gaining a more profound viewpoint into the grieving process and its significance to people's psychological and emotional well-being. Suppose grief is recognized as a process that occurs over time, and how that process looks are known. In that case, it is possible to let the researchers pinpoint the patterns and trends that might be characteristic of the grief process at one or another stage of the grieving process. Understanding their grief processes may help identify specialized prevention and intervention services and appropriate time to offer them to the bereaved (Moss et al., 2021, p.66). Further, knowledge of the duration of grief results in the realization of the lost time to study how people constitute their lives after the grief and identify the resources and coping mechanisms helpful for restoring the lost balance.

In addition, this section will look at how time and only comes to influence people's grief and their adjustment to bereavement. Stages of grief may also be characterized by changes in feeling, thinking, and behaving as one goes through this mourning process as time elapses (Parkes & Murray, 2020, pp. 241-253). Such concepts may include alterations in levels of grief symptoms, alterations in ways of managing stress, and changes in perceptions of the deceased and or the loss. Analyzing these temporal dimensions of grief, this work will explore the nature of time and adaptation in the context of loss. It will contribute to the understanding of the effects of loss on people's lives in the long run.

Key Findings

Themes of Grief Experience

This section elaborates on the nature of grief experience inferred from the identified themes and altitudinal subthemes. It is tasked to explain the outcomes of the student's interviews while focusing on the two major abstract concepts identified in the tapestry of idiographic grief patterns. Embedded in this analysis are the multiple emotions participants conveyed, from doubt and anger to grief and loss, acceptance, and hope (Barboza et al., 2022, pp. 7-24). Finally, there is a realization of one's self in the depths of such or another shade of grief because it helps to explain why grief responses are so intricate and complex. Furthermore, this section highlights how participants survived the stormy mourning world. While relying on social contacts and striving for companionship to being able to sit quietly alone, they were all tenacious in searching for some meaning and purpose in life when bereavement had uprooted them.

Furthermore, the following section explores Social Support as crucial to the grieving process. This is because participants described how supportive relationships offer reassurance, acknowledgment, and inclusion when individuals lose their bearings deeply. However, lack or

insufficiency of social support was cited as one of the significant areas of difficulty, according to the patient, which worsened the already prevailing feelings of loneliness and hopelessness. This section, demonstrating subtleties in the characterization of social support, underlines the role of community and relatedness as crucial to the bereavement process in patients. Besides, it shows how people and their meanings may be changed drastically at the same time when the loss takes place. They spoke about pondering life and growing to realize what matters most or choosing a new direction after a tragic loss. Listening to their stories, we learn about the fundamental existential dilemmas and existential development that can be a part of grieving, which shows the constructive aspect of the grieving process.

In other words, this section provides an overview of grief as a complex psychological process and a tragic life event with numerous psychological, social, and spiritual aspects (De Stefano et al., 2021, pp. 492-499). It enhances participants' literacy by identifying the main themes of the data and reveals how people can experience grief amidst its vagaries. These changes included outgroup rejection, intense emotional experiences that caused personal upheaval, significant shifts in identity, and the giving and finding of meaning, all of which brought into sharp focus the participants' resilience, flexibility, and ability to view growth as a possible outcome of the adversity they experienced. Grieving focuses on the human aspects of healing and underscores the importance of hope, relationships, and purpose toward recovery and restoration.

Perceptions of Grief Therapy

It is, therefore, important to understand participants' experiences and impressions to define grieving. This area is involved as this paper delves into the participants' perceptions of grief therapy. This section is conceived as a paradigm shift to show the benefits and burdens people encounter when they seek professional support when grieving. It investigates introductory

experiences involving participation, such as when a participant is willing to receive help, when and how varying treatments are chosen, and how satisfied they are with their assistance. In this exploration, the focus is to consider things that motivated or demotivated them regarding willingness or reluctance towards therapy, going past the apparent rationale (White & Victor, 2023). The remaining puzzle is how the culture of seeking help for mental illness in the United States and the associated reputational costs within society can influence those grieving. Finally, this section addresses the barriers to therapy services by exploring the influence of socioeconomic factors. It also explores participants' perceptions regarding the efficacy of different therapeutic approaches, including how those participants' epiphanies inform their attitudes toward grief therapy.

When it comes to grieving, people traverse the labyrinth of endowment and mourning therapies, far and wide, bequeathing different ways of coping with the ordeal. This segment could help shed a more comprehensive light on participants' experiences and interactions with diverse therapeutic approaches, including formal and informal therapy, psychological treatment styles like art therapy, and mindful practices (Soard & Jonathan, 2021). The section analyzes participants' experiences and reveals the impact of various therapeutic approaches on grieving people. Hence, it aims to explore the participants' perceptions of the different treatments, showing the specific advantages and drawbacks of each activity carried out during the occupation. Moreover, the section aims to expand the understanding of the participants' satisfaction with the support they received. It describes the factors that may enhance perceived therapy helpfulness and effectiveness of sessions. By identifying and studying participants' experiences, this study should provide valuable recommendations for further development of practice and services in the oncology support field and grief therapy.

When participants engage in grief therapy, they may also bring their characteristics into the setting regarding how the therapeutic process should be approached. In an attempt to receive participants' unique treatment choices, this segment explores the most effective and meaningful therapeutic modalities in addressing participants' choices of specific therapeutic approaches like cognitive behavioral, narrative, and group. The section endeavors to identify the rationales for such preferences. Further, it explores the participants' evaluation of the similarity of their therapeutic preferences with family and friends' satisfaction, as well as examining their previous experiences of caring for mental health. Moreover, the section under discussion aims to reveal participants' recommendations for possible development of grief therapy services and good suggestions for further improvement and idea generation (Garten et al., 2020, p. 67). Through amplification, this exploration seeks to contribute to the evidence base of participant needs and preferences so that grief therapy interventions can be better developed to meet their needs.

Challenges in Coping with Grief

During mourning, people face all sorts of issues and obstacles each of these requires strength to cope with grief (Carr et al., 2020, pp. 425-431). This section analyzes the web of challenges that participants deal with as they navigate the tortuous nature of mourning. Regarding challenges that interfere with life, especially in the present, intrusive thoughts stand tall, disrupting the serenity that engulfed the mind's privacy. Such obsessive thoughts are as bright as watching a reality show and come unannounced and uncondensed as a video clip of the deceased, which produces a slash of pain. Emotional numbing is another formidable foe; it ties people up in a cocoon of apathy and removes them from the possibility of feeling and understanding their emotions appropriately. While a helpful coping mechanism attached to retaliation, fear safeguards

individuals from feeling too much pain as it also keeps them from authentically operating in the real world.

Social isolation rears itself as a formidable foe, obstructing the connection between people and their sources of comfort and reducing their quality of life through isolation. Any loss usually opens a vast and lonely space in the middle of an individual, where it becomes challenging to find the other person or people who were so close to the grieving person, be it a friend, a family member, or even a pet (Jones & Lynne, 2020, pp.123-149). However, prominence moves in another direction: the weight of existential questions is a burden that overcasts the very existence of existence. Characters are forced to deal with existential questions provoked by a fatal question about human existence and one's life after death. While intrinsically humanistic, these philosophical thoughts can compound the innovative grief and thrust the person into novel existential solitude or new existential suffering and new existential turmoil.

Besides these central issues, other forms of stress increase the pressures and strains, another factor that causes the collapse of people losing their loved ones. The quantitative amount of money makes financial pressure a pervasive stressor, bringing up a sense of insecurity and instability in people's financial protection. Another strong barrier is the legal issues that follow the experience of loss, which results in putting people through a system of proper legalities and court cases (McGilloway et al., 2020, pp.51-66). Further, the alterations in the roles that people inhabit blur the continuity of life and lead to changes in the roles and places of the people in the universe after losing their loved ones. Although these secondary stressors are deemed to be less severe or profound than the primary ones, they do have a bearing on which grief-related problems a person can solve and, subsequently, the severity of their distress, as well as the progress of their grieving process.

Where there is loss, one can observe that people exhibit a range of ways through which they try to offset the various challenges of grief and ensure that they can endure the storms that come with the act of grieving. These varied strategies expose the tenacity of humanity or human strength focused on facing the challenge. Join mindfulness practices here, thinking only of the present and accepting whatever feels or comes with no judgment resistance, feelings, or anxiety (Pann et al., 2023, pp. 293-307). Some people tend to cry on paper, which means they write letters to their friends and loved ones whom they have lost or paint paintings, play music, or create poetry that helps them express and release the bitterness of their hearts. Also, asking friends or relatives for help or joining a support group can be a life-sustaining experience since people will hear from others and find a companion facing the same loss. In conclusion, everyone's mourning experience comprises psychological and sociological factors, but their strength to get through the night is real.

Support Systems and Social Networks

Bereavement is anchored on support systems and social networks as these capabilities offer supporting structures, companionship, and solace to mourning (Luong & Michele, 2021). This topic explores the common and diverse facets of Social Support, the types of support given by different people in the society, and the main types of support from the family, friends, and the community. It is why most people always run to their family members for comfort since they are the only ones who will always accept you the way you are and without asking any questions, regardless of what you are going through. It may involve concrete tasks like grocery shopping, home chores, financial assistance, child care, and emotional sessions, which include listening to the partner's feelings, affirming their feelings or matters that have made them sad, and even shared grief. Another source of support is friends and peers who accompany the grieving person and provide emotional and moral support with their understanding that they are no longer a complete

family. Residential support may also receive assistance from community centers, including religious or cultural groups, support organizations, and online forums to help fellow human beings undergoing the same experience.

It is important to comprehend the perceived usefulness of the different support sources and how these are linked to people's coping styles, as well as tenacity and adaptation to bereavement. Support may be said to be helpful, constructive and helpful to grievors, while there could be other forms of support that are being seen to be destructive or unhelpful and could even compound the problem. This section compares the effects of social support on coping and coping strategies of grieving people. The curricular research also demonstrates how social support can help individuals deal with the psychological consequences of loss; social backing is a form of protection that increases coping abilities, decreases the effects of grief and facilitates the process of recovery (Bowen et al., 2020). Social support is reinforcement messages in the form of social contacts or when people need help with specific tasks they need to accomplish. It cultivates the feeling of inclusiveness and wanting more, which adds to optimism and the attitude towards a better tomorrow.

Although social support has multiple advantages, those with social backing also face specific issues and constraints that influence grieving and the availability of assistance (Crowley & Andrea, 2022). It also considers factors that may limit the ability of the person to seek and get support, such as stigmatization, weak communication, and shifts in relationships. Cultural beliefs about grief and other mental health symptoms may leave persons in isolation and loneliness since they are ashamed to come forward to seek assistance or even share their feelings with other people. Interpersonal communication problems, including the manifestations of the degree of social integration demonstrated by an inability to explain, feel, or ask for help, can interfere with efficient

interaction with support providers and prevent receiving the requisite support. Interpersonal transitions incline alterations in relationships like family or social interactions, which deny them support and put them off in their grief journey.

Meaning-Making and Posttraumatic Growth

It is an ordinary and potentially necessary process of grief and mourning to search for meaning and explain why one has experienced this type of loss (Martin, Karen & Elder, 2020, pp.73-86). This section examines the complex and often painful process of making sense of loss, which, in this study, is conceptualized as participants' attempts at coherently understanding and giving meaning to their plight to find comfort and purpose. It explores both the elements of quest and narrative as it pertains to meaning, seeking, finding, and assigning meaning to the events and my life when the drastic loss of my father has left me in a state of profound disarray. Qualitative content analysis enables us to examine the range of approaches utilized by participants after an existential crisis and the finding of the emotional loss.

In addition, this section will discuss the notion of posttraumatic growth, which is essentially when the possibility of transformation that can be buried in and masked by the experience of trauma is discussed by Reynolds and Anne (2020). In this context, it is crucial to note that people manage to change for the better and note vital positive shifts in their lives despite the immense pain and suffering bound to grief. By curtailing participants' stories, they reveal how they have risen above their suffering to embrace achievements, flexibility, and knowledge. This discourse raises the question of the inherent bearings of humanity to rise and work towards finding solutions when they are faced with unbelievable calamities.

Also, a focus on positive psychological change indicates what promotes growth and human healing and shows how people can gain new strength after adversity. Concerning the critical

features of the story, it is essential to pinpoint the elements of hope, introspection, and individual existential perspectives as the factors that facilitate change in the main character (Tal et al., 2023, pp. 1-16). Source generating lies in the participants' experience; therefore, their data can be valuable in understanding factors that support resilience and contribute to the survivor's growth. In this way, we better understand these processes, eventually enlightening how individuals build resilience and thrive in the aftermath of such events.

Thematic Analysis

Identification of Major Themes

This study identified several overarching categories that summarize the participants' multidimensional views on mourning and loss. This study identified numerous trends or co-variables; one common culture is evident: 'grief.' It was reported that participants feel sad, angry, guilty, and anxious, which indicates the multifaceted and contradicting notions of loss. This theme demonstrates the situation's capacity to vary and intensify, stressing that grief is unique to every person. This is because some of the quotes collected from the participants summarized the depth of the feelings they have, such as the feeling of drowning in sorrow, being unable to see any ray of hope or the example given by another participant who observes that sometimes, grief makes one feel so sad, at other times angry or even indifferent.

Another critical area observed in the study's thematic analysis is social support, which addresses how people cope with grief (Harrop et al., 2020, pp. 871-888). Many participants emphasized that having a network of people to turn to in the form of family, friends, and even community members was crucial in assisting grieving people. This theme holds that humans 'need other humans to offer support and consolation and help in decision-making when faced with loss. Using quotes from the participants, the importance of social support in Nursing grief is brought to

the limelight: love and may never know how I would have got through this without it, but ‘I feel like I’m carrying this sorrow alone and it is choking me’ are testaments to the role of social support in mitigating grief and enhancing healing.

Emotional Responses to Grief

This involves acknowledging a host of emotional responses that are unique to the person and versatile in their display across the grieving stage. As for the range of emotions identified among the participants, one cannot even imagine that grief is much more complex than sorrow. Unlike what is generally observed in grief, for which deep sorrow is observed, participants in this study have described various feelings such as anger, guilt, anxiety, and numb feelings.

These may vary in their levels and span, as is expected of grieving, involving various feelings. Trauma survivors may quickly transition from denial to grief relief, which may be punctuated by hopelessness and worthlessness (Williams et al., 2021). In other cases, others may experience a deluge of cyclonic emotions, including anger, resentment or anger, guilt, and regret. It would be essential to grasp the range of feelings of the grievers to become well-equipped because the feelings expressed are deep and broad in this natural grieving process.

Since grieving is a natural process, there can be internal and external factors that may either increase the intensity or variability of the emotional reactions. Emotional reactions are also influenced by the nature of the loss, for example, the abruptness of death, the familial or social closeness, and how the loss occurred (Benson et al., 2022). For instance, when one loses a beloved one to a sudden death, one's emotions are shocked, more so when the death is unexpected, leading to confusion and hopelessness. As in the case of intimacy and attachment, the proximity and connection of the loved one are known to magnify the degree of suffering and yearning felt by the survivor. Further, by incorporating community, social support, coping, and cultural factors, one

can gain an understanding of whether these factors may enhance or, conversely, amplify the level of emotional distress an individual may experience.

Emotional support is another crucial aspect of how people process their grief, as it is the source of comfort, reassurance, and mutual recognition during the most painful events of their lives. Cultural support mechanisms that are available enable the isolated grief person to open up to friends and family to share their feelings of loss and reflect on the circumstances of the deceased (Glykioti, Konstantina & Figueroa, 2021). On the other hand, social isolation or perceived lack of social support may make a person feel sadder and more hopeless, which adds to the psychological weight of grieving. Moreover, grief management strategies that the given people use are also an indicator of the degree and time frame of emotional experiences. Thus, adaptive processing of emotions implies social support, self-care activities, and the search for meaning in the mourner's experience (Adelstein, Katharine & Archer-Nanda). On the other hand, denial and other careless strategies of coping with stress, like the use of substances or emotional numbing, help give the individual a little relief. Still, they are not helpful in the grieving process and prolong the symptoms of distress.

Coping Mechanisms and Strategies

Grieving is an intricate and private experience that may depend on many factors, including, though not limited to, the cause of loss, one's personality, and available resources (Ang & Siang, 2023, pp. 12975-12987). Here, the actual coping self-identified by the participants and methods the participants used to come to terms with their loss by burying a loved one will be described. Another of the most frequently cited stress-attack coping strategies reported by the participants was the initiative to seek social support. However, in stress management, ecological support entails asking for emotional, practical, and instrumental support from such sources as family members,

friends, support groups, or mental health professionals (Chronister et al., 2021, p.87). People can gain comfort by having others to lean on and receive affirmations from under challenging situations through support. Most participants feel comfort and relief when they express or talk to others since they realize they are not alone in grieving.

Taking part in self-care activities is another coping mechanism utilized more often by participants when grieving (Esplen et al., 2022, p.55). This may include actions to engage in self-care, including physical, emotional, and spiritual exercise, stretching, hobby, meditation, and artistic creation. It helps break the spell of grief and gives time and energy, and individuals learn to be good to themselves and strong for themselves. In supporting participants' self-care, they can also do activities in which they get satisfaction and have what they need to address grief accordingly, with good morale and professional help.

Grieving and seeking purpose in the loss is one of the major themes identified in the overall processes of mourning revealed by the vast majority of participants (Taylor & Steven 2021, p. 318). This includes coming to meaning, coping with the loss, searching for meaning, and reconstructing meaning in the individual's life story and orientation to the world. People find meaning in suffering in diverse ways, pursuing meaning, providing values, cherishing the memory of the lost, and seeking new experiences in transition (Becker & Gay, 2023). Since the loss is conceptualized as a lens through which participants define themselves and find new meaning and passion in life, they feel hopeful and can transform their grief process.

The experience of grief is not well-defined, and participants may engage in both healthy and unhealthy ways of handling the situation to ease the pain (Skrozic, Amna & Kijamet, 2022, pp. 13-27). A coping style that has been described as pathological in cross-sectional research is the denial of the grief process. One is the tendency to avoid stimuli that remind them of the

deceased. This could be by shunning people, places, or items related to the deceased or through substance use and other addictive behaviors to deaden the pain of grief. This signifies that although diagnostic removal may offer a short-term reprieve from distress, it inhibits the grieving process and retains unresolved feelings of grief. Furthermore, there are bound to be difficulties and obstacles to competent handling of grief by participants, for instance, shame, inability to access grief support, or may come from a culture that does not support mourning. This section aims to represent all possible ways one can approach their grieving process and all potential factors that may affect this process and the outcome, including using healthy and dysfunctional coping mechanisms.

Social Support and Interpersonal Relationships

Grieving involves several essential elements, such as social support and interpersonal relationships, as they offer communal, tangible advice to grieving people (Plaud, Cécile & Urien, 2022, pp. 154-167). It is critical to note that family members, friends, and other members of the community play a crucial role in providing emotional and even tangible support to bereaved families. People require a companion who can listen to their feelings and offer them some consolation, which is often needed after the loss of a loved one since the grieving process demands the expression of feelings of sadness and anger, as well as confusion. Practical help including house chores, car, monetary assistance, and taking care of the children helps in the discharge of task that may hinder the grieving process of the individual concerned. Tangible support on the part of assuring, giving directions, and making available resources facilitates the individual in arriving at an informed one and making decisions about the course to follow while grieving.

This general idea points out that the perceived helpfulness of social support is a function of the nature and quality of the social bonds under consideration. Husband, wife, parents, and

siblings share a closer relationship with their loved ones, and they stand by the mourners and provide compassion. People our age and near to us may be able to give emotional support, occupy the mind, and make it easier to adapt to all changes in a grieving person's life. Churches, mosques, synagogues, culturally relevant supportive societies, social media platforms, and online groups also provided the client avenues to encounter other individuals going through similar ordeals, hence validation, acceptance, and fellowship.

Support has a bearing on people's coping behaviors and adaptation processes regarding loss in several ways. Social support can improve people's ability to deal with stress and independently deal with the sources of pressure, making it easier for them or helping them find ways to deal with those sources (Bavik et al., 2020, pp. 726-758). The first hypothesis posited that high social integration and solid social relationships ensure people feel they belong, creating satisfaction that leads to psychological well-being. On the other hand, low or poor social support increases loneliness and distress levels, and individuals' ability to cope with the process of grieving is hampered (Cakar & Savi, 2020, pp. 27-40). Social support requires distinguishing between positive and negative surrogacy, receptivity, and mutual support, as these factors can influence grieving mechanisms.

Loss often involves shifts in personal relationships, which can significantly alter the grieving process (Taylor & Steve, 2021, p.381). Grief may affect the existing roles and responsibilities within a family or other cooperative social systems, causing changes in the rate and styles of communication. Failure in marriage and other forms of marital relationships, such as civil partnerships, for instance, losing a beloved spouse, can lead to the feeling of loneliness due to the loss of a life partner. Similarly, none of the family members knows how to cope with the loss of a parent or child, which causes tension in the family and affects the individual's position in

the family. It is also essential to investigate the effects of alterations in social roles on bereaved people as these changes affect the availability of support and coping with grief, especially when people feel isolated or rejected (Hansen et al., 2024, pp. 465-477). Notably, one must acknowledge that such relationships undergo alterations during the period of grieving, and it's crucial for the healthcare staff and support services to adapt to that and address the evolving needs of users.

Meaning-Making and Personal Growth

Grief, therefore, constitutes a multifaceted phenomenon that people go through to make sense of what has happened and grow from the experience of loss. In this section, the authors explore the participants' perceived sense-making of grief and how they conceptualize meaning and purpose in the face of loss. Pivotal to this discovery is the phenomenon of posttraumatic growth, which acts to visually disseminate the possibility of positive psychological changes following traumatic events (Villalobos & Cruz, 2020). The paper's findings show that the meaning-making process is complex and multifaceted, validating participants' examination of values, beliefs, and life priorities. By doing so, people face existential issues and seek meaning and an understanding of their losses.

Coping with loss involves the process of grieving, and the notion of posttraumatic growth provides guidelines to consider the rehabilitative aspect of grief. If one looks at the study from a survivor's perspective, they also remember positive changes and strong coping in the face of significant trauma. They describe how the hard times fostered the seeds of the strength, inspiration, and vision arising within themselves. Participants discuss the subjects of strength, acceptance, and gratitude to exhibit how different grief phases contribute to forming their behaviors and beliefs. PTG is not the mere lack or absence of pain or suffering (Taylor & Emily, 2022). Still, it is an

indication of the willingness to make something constructive out of the hostile experience or trauma and is therefore action-oriented with appropriate coping strategies.

Psycho-social work in fostering meaning-making and growth after loss is a complex process based on various factors (Chokhani et al., 2024, pp. 103-131). Support contrastively appears necessary for fostering coping and resilience in grief processes. Most interpersonal interactions have been described as having a more profound influence on how individuals cope with the challenges associated with the mourning process, as supported by the following excerpt (Lai et al., 2021). Maintaining relationships with family and friends and community relations offers support and relieves anxiety by letting the grieving individual feel supported, accepted, and wanted during their mourning. In addition, spirituality or even existential concepts can help an individual cope with loss out of the suffering they experience. Patients find comfort and meaning in religious and otherwise beliefs and turn to philosophical or existential musings to locate a silver lining amidst trials and tribulations.

The significance of meaning-making and personal growth concerning individuals' psychological adaptation, well-being, and quality of life is immense and cannot be underestimated (Jones & Hillary, 2021). To eliminate the isolation from grief, participants reveal how gaining insight developed empathy, compassion, and relatedness. These include perceiving more value in minor aspects of existence and older aspects and re-establishing the meaning of existence. In addition, the participants express the necessity of proper self-care and the development of resilient behaviors for psychological health, which has to be maintained after the experience of the loss. In turn, mindfulness, self-compassion, and self-reflection are highlighted as helpful resources in providing skills for coping with grief and building up one's emotional strength (Vahradyan et al.,

2024). Lastly, understanding how meaning is made and growth and change occur is a positive message about the human spirit's ability to rebuild and transform after traumatic experiences.

DISCUSSION

Introduction

The extensive tables in the appendices clearly show this research's data collection and analysis procedures. These tables represent the numerous sensations and opinions of grieving people and those whose work is to help grieving clients, which can provide essential information about grief and therapeutic methods targeting this problem.

Interview Questions for Bereaved Individuals

The first table summarized the qualitative data captured from the bereaved people as they stated the multiple emotional terrains they have to deal with after losing their loved ones. They talked about the positive effects of the film and expressed poor feelings, which included sadness, Anger, and a sense of calm sometimes. The differences highlighted here emphasize that people grieve differently, so it is crucial to have Person-Centered therapies. Diverse self-care strategies: Specific ways participants dealt with the situation included supporting family and friends, practicing self-care, and attending support group meetings (Stapley et al., 2020, pp. 605-632). These findings underscore the importance of grief therapy and the critical effort to enhance such applications involving different treatment approaches based on the specific client's needs.

A few participants received considerable support through professional assistance in their therapy services, while others had difficulties procuring adequate services. That suggests the need to enhance accessibility and adapt grief therapy to respond to the demands of grief individuals (Iglewicz et al., 2020, pp.90-98). Furthermore, analysis of participants' feedback pointed to the following defensive factors deemed necessary by participants for therapists to bear in mind: Empathy Validation and Culture. Indeed, these findings suggest the growing need to enhance

training programs for grief therapists, where applying these qualities in handling the bereaved is paramount so that they can offer the required support to the clients.

Interview Questions for Psychologists

The second table is somewhat related to the first one as it looks at the psychologists' practice, the issues they face, and the practices they use in their everyday work. Counselors and psychologists emphasized the challenges facing grief therapy, pointing to issues of diversity, regional differences, the impact of emotions, and other existential factors (Ivers et al., 2024). The mention of the numerous therapy modalities like narrative therapy or mindfulness-based interventions shows the need and demand for versatility in grief therapy. To address the complexities of grief, these findings imply that training programs for psychologists should provide exposure to a broader spectrum of interventions.

Psychologists also recalled their stories about the course of developed therapy, which showed that people in this profession should develop continuous learning and critical thinking (Ziede, Jake & John, 2020, pp. 585-618). This follows the goals set in this study: to ensure that grief therapists are offered a constant learning process and flexibility in handling patients. Additionally, more prescriptions that the psychologists highlight about future research encompass exploring new therapies and cultural differences in grieving, demonstrating the significant areas of study that could be useful in refining grief operations.

Interview Questions for Counselors

The findings of counselors are elaborated on in the third table, which includes rapport, therapeutic techniques, and multicultural competencies. Counselors would also take a lot of time to provide safe and supportive environments by listening to clients' responses and substantiating them with proper empathy (Dave & Tanvi, 2021). This points to the importance of the working

alliance in grief therapy, as discussed earlier. The practice of the counselors, from expressive arts therapy to fun activities, including mindfulness exercises, made me understand that grieving clients require various approaches to assist them.

Two other significant areas of concern were cultural sensitivity and ethical practice. Concerning cultural relevance and sensitivity, the counselors argued that the training programs should include cultural aspects due to diversity in society so counselors can know how to manage the sessions (Sue et al., 2022). These ethical issues, as highlighted above, are a clear testimony of the importance of intensive ethical training and supervision for practitioners involved in grief therapy. The precautionary ACS self-care, which the counselors incorporate, is the impact of their approach on grieving clients and the recognition of the necessity of measures against therapist burnout.

Interview Questions for Social Workers

The fourth table analyses the field of social workers' view, focusing on the social determinants of health and systemic issues as the intersections of the grieving process. Participants also underscored socio-economic predictors, physical health, and access to care as influential in grief processes. This shows why grief therapy must account for such societal factors in its global model that seeks to help the grieving. Examining systematic barriers means that advocacy and community resources should be crucial for grieving persons, especially those of less privileged backgrounds.

Social workers' discussion of cultural competence regarding the population expands the understanding of the need for Cultural competence and active Cultural humility in grief therapy (Asnaani & Anu, 2023). These interactions with diverse clients and communities support the continuous commitment to learning about their distinct needs and the importance of building

partnerships with local stakeholders to serve clients better. The directions mentioned by social workers for the improvement of practices, for example, to ensure increased accessibility of support services for grieving people or the inclusion of holistic approaches, are pertinent for future practice and studies.

Data Collection Methods Table

The methods used in the Data Collection Methods table show that the study has employed sound and rigorous methods alongside observing ethical considerations. It describes how participants will be recruited, with particular emphasis on the use of purposive sampling in an attempt to gain a wide-ranging view of the topic under study. The recruitment strategies also take measures that ensure that participants clearly understand what they are willing to participate in. Keeping their identification anonymous is an ethical manner of handling participants since it protects their rights and well-being.

The unstructured and relatively open nature of interviews used in the current study enabled a detailed description of the participants' experience: the interviewees were asked concrete questions requiring further elaboration to provide additional information or clarification. Participant observation allowed data to be collected from the participants' environment, documents were analyzed to support the findings, and interviewees' experiences revealed multiple practices in grief and therapy. The researcher kept this data safe and secure and ensured the typing was accurate, thus making the study results credible and ethical.

Finally, the appendices with detailed tables contribute to the value of the discussion by introducing some comprehension of the data retrieving and examination procedures. They focus on the variability of the sorrow and growth of the loss survivors and practitioners interested, demonstrating that there is no proper way of grieving. They serve multiple purposes, such as

contributing to the understanding and development of grief therapy as a field, ensuring that support for grieving is enhanced, and guiding prospective work within the scientific and professional communities.

Interpretation of Results

Explanation of the Major Themes Identified

As the specific findings of the results section are explored for their meaning and significance, extending into an appreciation of the interpretation of the data and the major themes, it becomes increasingly apparent that grief is a complex phenomenon. One of the major issues highlighted is that grief is manifested with a range of emotions (Alvis et al., 2023, pp. 447-457). The above analysis shows that grief is a complex, open-ended, and often intense experience and that participants described and experienced only sadness, Anger, guilt, and anxiety but in varying degrees of intensity. This theme emphasizes that emotions in mourning processes differ and vary at different times after loss. Depending on the nature of the loss, social support can be provided to the bereaved and how they have coped with it (Cakar & Savi, 2020, pp. 27-40).

Furthermore, the frequency and the fluctuations of effects indicate that the grieving process is not static and stable over time, undermining one of the critical assumptions of grief as a linear and predictable concept. This research underscores the significance of acknowledging, appreciating, and respecting various emotions in grieving persons. It also reminds us of the appropriateness of applying individualized and versatile strategies in delivering grief counseling.

Another noteworthy emerging theme is the possession and implementation of coping mechanisms and strategies during mourning periods. The study identified that self-care and support from friends and family members were most familiar with dealing with the loss. However, some participants used alcohol to block out the feelings of grief, while others tried not to remind

themselves that their loved one was gone (Drabwell et al., 2020, p.677). Again, this highlights the substitutional and dysfunctional coping processes that foster the development of resources and promote growth, as well as those that maintain difficulties and avoidant processes. The coping resources used by participants in this study indicated a significant difference in the effectiveness of the coping resources in reducing grief-related distress in different participants, implying that understanding and attending to participants' needs while designing interventions requires a multitier contextual analysis. Additionally, stigma, lack of social support and or resources, and inability to effectively apply coping measures also resulted in poor coping, which raises the question of the role of systems and structures in the loss process and coping.

Moreover, it became apparent that reestablishing social support and interpersonal relationships was also crucial in the grieving process (Plaud, Cecile & Urien, 2022, pp. 154-167). Interviewees stated that they required support from friends, families, and their community, asserting that procedural social support helps reduce the adverse effects of loss and enables coping mechanisms. Nevertheless, participants also put forward different aspects of social support and the difficulties and problems that arise, for example, isolation and stigmatization, as well as how communication may be affected after bereavement. This theme points to the complexity of discussing social support in grief therapy. It highlights the value of exploring relation and cultural factors that may shape support's meaning and experiences for grieving persons.

Integration with Existing Literature

Connecting with the current literature is another approach to localizing this study on grief and bereavement and the findings. As with most areas of psychosocial and psychosocial psychology, grief and bereavement can now boast a vast volume of scholarly, theoretical, and empirical literature, as well as accumulating clinical data. The study of this literature can offer a

great deal to anyone interested in the subject (Stroebe, Margaret & Schut, 2021, pp. 500-522). When comparing and contrasting the targets of this research study with targets identified in prior research studies, the similarities and differences in the objectives can be comprehended and explained. It avails this integration process, and we can better understand the different enablers and suppressors of grief-related experiences, thereby enhancing theory construction and lightning in the fields.

Another issue when using the analysis results to continue existing studies is to find out what patterns we revealed in this case, whether they are familiar or differentiated. From the previous studies on grief and bereavement, some of the themes that have been found include Anger, which is an emotion that is commonly found in grievors, where they feel that they have been deprived. Bereaved persons always require support from their close friends and relatives (Trouton et al., 2020, pp. 18-23). The grievors always try to seek the meaning of their loss. In identifying how these themes align with the current study, we hope to offer data corroboration and strengthen the knowledge database within the healthcare field. In addition, we can examine variations in these themes across populations, cultures, and contexts, helping to understand individual grief and the range of losses people face.

In the same manner that areas of comorbidity are essential, so too is the consideration of divergence and contradictory studies. For instance, while much research is aimed at stressing the crucial role of social support in enabling coping with loss, other research is focused on revealing the insufficiency of the support network. In availing of such discrepancies, we can identify other possible sources of variation where research methodologies, sample characteristics, and conceptual frameworks may differ. Through critical self-reflection, one can identify specific

aspects of grief and bereavement that require improvements, possibly from theoretical, empirical, and or even methodological angles.

Besides, integrating the findings with existing literature enables the researcher to point out the gaps and the research areas to be conducted in the future. A review of the existing literature on grieving and bereavement reveals many gaps that have remained uncovered and many issues that require further investigation. For instance, even though the current literature may contain relevant data concerning the short-term consequences of grief, there may be scant data on the long-term effects of grief as well as the protective factors that determine positive psychosocial outcomes such as resilience and posttraumatic growth in the course of the grief process (Hopf & Dora, 2023). The current study's findings revealed several limitations that can help plan future research and encourage further investigation of novel directions concerning grief and bereavement.

Implications for Grief Therapy Practice

Considering the guidelines for utilizing grief therapy outlined in the study, the implications are vast and complex. Firstly, the findings in the study are very beneficial in modifying the therapeutic interventions to adequately fit the grieving persons' needs. Being aware of the variety of feelings, ways of dealing with stress, and how people support each other presented in the present study makes therapists more sensitive to the client's needs to accord the client a more client-centered therapy (Lakioti et al., 2020, p.560). When clients' distinct stories alongside respective difficulties are acknowledged, therapists should extend respective treatment approaches based on their clients' wants, interests, and cultural identities. This model is person-centered, thus enabling a solid therapeutic relationship with the client to render effective grief therapy.

Second, it is suggested the necessity to pay attention to the problems related to coping with grief as the revealed results stem from the therapeutic processes. Therapists are advised to actively

ensure that patients improve their coping strategies by avoiding activities and substances that only aggravate the situation and acts of denying that there exists a problem (Yildiz, Erman & Aylaz, 2021, pp. 390-404). The client and clinicians can work together to recognize negative coping mechanisms, search for other strategies, and help the client develop a more effective coping style when dealing with new adversities. Cognitive-behavioral therapy, mindfulness, and narrative therapy might be incorporated, as all these practices have a self-focused problem-solving approach that can help grief clients manage their loss in a practical and more controlled way.

In addition, the study's results contribute to knowledge about the possibility of strengthening resilience and the process of positive psychological change after trauma in grievers. In identifying lagging factors that appear to help individuals create meaning and grow spiritually, therapists can assess the goals of treatment that are necessary to prescribe interventions that would enhance psychological well-being and positive adaptation after loss (Hood & Robert, 2022). This could include helping clients engage with perceptions of meaning and purpose in the aftermath of loss, promoting consideration over personal resourcefulness and beliefs, helping develop strengths and resources required to cope with difficulties and pain, stressing the possibilities for positive change when mourning assists clients in being hopeful, optimistic, and empowered to continue the process of achieving better psychological and emotional states.

Furthermore, the implications of the study's results make it possible to notice the need for integrative and comprehensive approaches to grief therapy. Acknowledging that grief encompasses feelings and thoughts, behaviors, interpersonal and search for meaning, it encompasses emotional, cognitive, behavioral, social, and existential domains (Temiz & Ridvan, 2024, pp. 1-11). Therapists require an analytic and versatile approach to practice. This may encompass augmenting mix strategies and psychotherapy methods, including expressive arts

therapy, body-centered therapy, and existential psychotherapy to cater to the diverse client populations. Through the nurses' acknowledgment of the mind-body-spirit connection in the grieving process and their practice of using this holistic and transformative practice, we see how the quality of life of every person is enriched.

Clinical and Practical Applications

The practicality of the findings enhances their utility to clinicians and practitioners, focusing on those experiencing loss (Damarell et al., 2020, pp. 1-23). The first implication of these authors for grief therapy is the need to embrace person-centered care for patients. By understanding how each client may feel, perceive, and respond, clinicians can enhance the recovery process by providing individual appropriate methods of helping during the grieving process. The approach whereby the bereavement therapist gets to a point where the client can be trusted and lets them manage their grief process as they wish, not pressuring them into coming to terms with the loss and healing at their pace.

In addition, the results of the findings revealed that interdisciplinary treatments are valuable for managing complicated grief since the experience of the loss is complex in many cases. Clinicians need to adopt diverse treatments in that they may practice CBT, narrative therapy, mindfulness-based therapy, and expressive art therapies (Lopez & Gabrielle, 2024). These approaches provide various ideas on how to express as well as how to manage grieving cognitions, feelings, and behaviors and assist with facilitating coping skills, posttraumatic growth, and recuperative personal resources.

Culture is still another central component of delivering good grief therapy services. This means that clinicians must understand the cultural factors underlying how people grieve and the cultural factors that dictate how grieving is done (Silverman & Gila, 2021, pp. 1-8). This means

being interested in being more culturally attuned all the time and perpetually enriching one's cultural competence. The cultural relevance of therapeutic interventions can be successfully achieved and implemented by recognizing the culture of end-of-life losers. They can be adjusted to meet the client's needs and culture, thus facilitating effective therapeutic services.

Another attribute that is valuable to work on in Grief therapy practice is Ethics. Ethical practice involves the clinician behaving ethically (Park et al., 2022, p. 1400). These include Autonomy, beneficence, non-maleficence, and justice toward the clients. This comprises the ability to seek and obtain valid consent, respect and protect the privacy and confidentiality of the client, act competently and professionally, and where there is any possibility of conflict of interest or cross-over of boundaries. Furthermore, ethical situations may sometimes occur. Clinicians should adhere to risk factors that may cause harm to the clients and take the necessary precautions in addressing the issue.

Another important aspect of this collaboration is that grief therapy requires a combination of inter-professional teamwork, where different professionals can maximize their strengths by offering holistic and all-inclusive medical treatment to the patient. As a result, clinicians may improve their practice by engaging other professionals, including psychiatrists, social workers, chaplains, and grief counsellors, to help those who need it due to loss (Dodd et al., 2022, pp. 1329-1337). A multidisciplinary approach leads to a more comprehensive client evaluation of their biological, psychological, and social-spiritual state and more effective and integrated treatment management. It is a fact that clinicians can establish relationships with community resources and support systems that can contribute to the constructive bereavement process for bereaved clients and their families.

Future Directions and Research Opportunities

The mental health profession has many cathedrals of growth when embarking on future directions and research opportunities in the study of grief (Hansford & Oliver, 2023). Another direction of concern in the subsequent studies may be the chronological patterns of grief investigation. Although the current study may have offered directions helpful in understanding the short-term manifestation of grief among participants, long-term qualitative studies could elicit more depth given the development of grief over time (Chen et al., 2023, pp. 788-808). It is the type of research that might document the grief responses of the bereaved at various stages of the grieving process or lack to establish the patterns of adaptation, resilience, and post-trauma growth. Other research approaches that would be advantageous for studying the dynamics of grief include prospective designs, which would facilitate the examination of factors that could affect the grief process course, including loss characteristics, social support, and coping styles.

Another potential avenue can be pre-defined cultural differences in the grieving process and manifestations of grief (Aeschlimann et al., 2024). It is imperative to acknowledge that culture plays a significant role in how people grieve. Thus, cross-cultural studies may reveal essential information on the specific cultural expectations of mourners and how these expectations are met. Comparing grief experiences from cross-cultural perspectives enables the researcher to find aspects of grief that are similar in all cultures and aspects that are only peculiar to specific cultures. It may be helpful and valuable in the establishment of cross-culturally sensitive and culturally appropriate grief therapy interventions, attitudes, and practices that embrace and value multiculturalism.

Moreover, it might also be possible to refine and conduct empirical studies on other forms of novel grief therapy approaches and delivery. Another potential avenue for subsequent studies,

based on findings from qualitative studies such as the present one, would be to develop and test preventive and therapeutic strategies focusing on selected facets of the grieving process (Kaplow et al., 2023). For example, interventions could be aimed at increasing coping ability, helping with finding meaning in suffering, strengthening support systems, or existential issues. There are several conceptual and methodological approaches for developing and implementing these interventions; however, experimental research, such as randomized controlled trials, could investigate the efficacy and practicality of these approaches in enhancing the well-being of the bereaved (Sarma et al., 2021). Besides, studies could examine how technology-supported interventions, including online-based groups or virtual reality therapy, could be employed in conventional grief therapy.

Besides further measuring specific content types, methodological approaches and study designs within the field of grief therapy should also be viewed. Possible developmental advances in research methodologies, such as the mixed-method paradigm, can provide a broader perspective for realizing grief by integrating qualitative and quantitative research and data collection and analysis procedures. Incorporating the various approaches in the study could make the process more productive in dealing with insight into the nature of grief (Gonzalez et al., 2022). Furthermore, another factor that should be featured in research is diversity, which means that researchers should ensure that their participant populations are diverse and representative.

Comparison with Existing Literature

Consistency and Divergence

When comparing the results of this study with the prior literature relating to grief and bereavement, one can pinpoint several commonalities that corroborate and strengthen the existing body of knowledge. One such consistency is that humans, for instance, emotionally react to grief similarly regardless of their origin (Goldstein et al., 2020). Also evident in the current study, as in the former case, is that the indexes of grief include symptoms such as sadness, Anger, guilt, and anxiety. This can be explained by the Kübler-Ross model of the grieving process, which states that people go through several states of mourning even if the states do not have a sequential order (Teh et al., 2022, pp. 172-176). The similarity in effects to previous work indicates the universality of grief and sheds light on the research's objective of recognizing mourners' emotions.

In addition, the study under discussion supports the previous empirical evidence about the role of social support in mourning. As earlier noted, lack of social support from families, friends, and the rest of the community is a significant determinant of grief. The current study revealed that participants focused on the need to get comfort and reassurance, as well as some practical help from primary and available sources of support, therefore confirming the results of several studies revealing a positive nature of the impact of social support during loss (Carter et al., 2021, pp.36-44). Receiving these consistencies highlights that maintaining positive interpersonal relationships and networks, hence drawing a positive relationship between the interpersonal environment and the grieving process, stresses the necessity of practical support for the interventions applied in grief therapy.

However, the current study pointed out several main and other significant differences, which have made discoveries regarding grief and bereavement. It is essential to compare one

significant deviation: the phenomenon of posttraumatic growth in the context of loss. Although quantitative research on grief has focused chiefly on the harm and the consequences of the identified process, including psychological distress and impaired functioning, the present research contributes to the understanding of the possibility of posttraumatic growth resulting from adversity. The study subjects stated that they had gained some strength and later understood life in their potential after experiencing grief.

Additionally, the current study contributes to the existing literature by highlighting the importance of meaning-making in the context of grief. Consistent with existential theories of grief, the study found that participants actively engaged in the search for meaning and purpose in the aftermath of loss. Through storytelling, legacy-building, and finding linings, participants sought to make sense of their experiences of grief and find meaning in their loss. This emphasis on meaning-making adds depth to our understanding of grief as a complex and multifaceted phenomenon, highlighting the grieving process's existential, spiritual, and philosophical dimensions (Temiz & Ridvan, 2024, pp. 1-11). Offering a new perspective on what is traditionally considered a negative experience, the notion of 'positive grief' shifted the focus from the suffering aspect of grief and encouraged recognizing the potential for personal growth that is contained in the grieving process.

Themes and Patterns Across Studies

Analysis of the results and findings of the studies in the field of grief indicates that there is more than one way to understand the grieving process (Avis et al., 2021). In the application process, one may discern various forms of affective reactions people show to the idea of loss. The research indicates that the clientele may experience emotions such as sadness, anger, or guilt, besides suffering severe anxiety when they have lost their loved ones. These emotions are

passionate and variable in many instances, particularly regarding the ability to cope functionally and physically. However, researchers have also established variability in emotional display and modulation in mourners and have used other evidence to indicate that the grieving process is unique to the person and depends on factors such as personality, attachment culture (Hoffmann et al., 2022, pp. 276-290) This is quite important as clinicians and researchers need to know what emotional themes to focus on to cope with the needs of grieving individuals who need interventions and support.

The last of the established themes within the grief literature includes strategies for dealing with the loss, where investigations seek to demonstrate how the grief process is managed. Several coping strategies, including using social support, performing pleasant activities, and perceiving benefits related to the loss, are found in the report as the identified ways of responding to grieving (Meichsner et al., 2020, pp.560-569). On the other hand, more constructive coping methods comprising optimism, acceptance, accommodation, and problem-solving are also present, but their psychological implications are unfavorable. However, researchers have pointed out more clearly coping with loss by stressing that coping may differ depending on the type of loss and the accessibility of social resources and personal resources. With such coping patterns determined, researchers can aid in the establishment of strategies for encouraging appropriate coping mechanisms to reduce the effects of unhealthy coping on grief.

Comfort-seeking becomes the most pervasive pattern when designating social support systems as the most significant concept in grief and its consequences. Cross-sectional research has a continuing indication of the role of social support in moderating the impact of grief and outcomes conducive to coping. This study agrees that families, friends, and community networks provide grievers with emotional, instrumental, and informational support (Cacciatore et al., 2021).

Furthermore, it is argued and found out by studies that it is not the number of perceived social support but rather the quality of that support that plays a crucial role in shaping the outcomes of grief and psychological well-being among those grieving. Research also emphasizes the dual nature of social support and its possible positive and negative effects on individuals, such as social pressures and conflicts. Examining the process by which social support networks unfold is of primary importance for clinicians and researchers interested in helping the bereaved find effective support systems and navigate the process of post-loss adaptation effectively.

Methodological Considerations

The chosen approach has emerged as a critical factor in assessing grief and bereavement investigations. Comparing the current study with similar studies indicates that the quality, reliability, and consistency of research findings depend on research design, sample selection strategies, data collection, and analysis techniques used in the research process. Another issue is the type of research being conducted, as this dictates the general process and strategy of data collection and analysis. The former can be qualitative investigations examining the subjects' experiences from interviews or focus groups. On the other hand, the latter employs quantifiable variables and hypotheses, employing surveys or experimentation. It is only by developing an appreciation of the advantages and disadvantages of each approach that it is possible to start to make some generalizations concerning the very existence and nature of grief.

Another approach is the sampling method used in research works. Census, probability, and non-probability samples affect the possibility of generalizing the findings, depending on the type of sampling, such as convenience, purposive, or random sampling. For example, research that employs the convenience type of sampling may include participants who are easily accessible, and this may lead to the use of subjects who are in no way a correct representation of the population

being studied (Mweshi, Kapasa & Sakyi, 2020). On the other hand, random sampling aims to obtain assorted participants from the target population, increasing the external research reliability. Suppose researchers conduct a similar study or review the available literature. In that case, they can evaluate the effectiveness of the sampling methods and determine the possible generalization of the obtained outcomes across various population groups and settings.

In addition to theoretical concepts, methodological issues correspond to data-gathering methods and analysis procedures. Another aspect concerning data generation is the technique used to gather data, which includes interviews, questionnaires, observation, or document review. Likewise, the type of analysis used, which can be qualitative, quantitative, or mixed-method, also determines how the data is analyzed and interpreted. For instance, in qualitative research, thematic analysis is used to explore textual data and categorize the data into various themes. In contrast, in quantitative research, several studies, such as hypothesis tests, are considered to estimate the relationships shared between variables (Borgstede, Matthias & Scholz, 2021, p. 605191). By comparing the data collection and analytical methods of the current study with that of data presented in similar literature, researchers may examine the quality and reliability of the data. They can also find ways to refine better and develop methods in future research on grief and bereavement.

Cultural and Contextual Factors

Social and cultural factors are instrumental in determining how grieving is conceived and manifested by those grieving. Therefore, the essence of grief can be captured in culture-specific norms, beliefs, and practices that guide people when they are bereaved. For instance, cultures such as Asian have a collectivistic orientation, and therefore, mourning has a communal aspect rather than personal (Im, Hyojin & Neff, 2021, pp. 99-113). It extends to cultural provisions of care and

support by the family and the community and the role of rituals and ceremonies in mourning. On the same wavelength, in collectivistic cultures, such as American culture, there might be a highly valued aspect regarding the need to grieve and cope with loss independently without much regard for others. Clinicians and practitioners who encounter such populations should understand these differences since this will enable them to address the mourners while respecting their cultural values.

However, grief is also affected by socio-economic status; it can affect people's experience of loss and may limit their access to resources that are required for mourning. For instance, people who come from humble backgrounds can be subjected to other stress factors or loss, and coping is equally challenging due to issues to do with poverty, poor or no insurance coverage, and no social support system (Juntunen et al., 2022, p.291). These characteristics could intensify feelings of loneliness and despair and hamper clients' capacity to find and obtain the necessary care services. Furthermore, differences in healthcare systems themselves, like unequal availability of mental health care and culturally sensitive care, only add to the problems that bereaved people from minority or underserved backgrounds experience. Thus, clinicians and practitioners must search for the specific socio-economic circumstances in which grief appears and seek to change systematic restrictions on equal access to grief support services.

Additionally, religious systems shape the griever's experience by guiding how people respond to loss and grief. The main focuses of social support are the restitution of hope, meaning given to death and suffering, and the outlining of the manners of existence after death. For example, rituals and ceremonies involving death and mourning, as observed in religion, are not only forms of devotion but also ways of helping the grieving (Mulemi & Benson, 2020, pp. 1520-1524). Furthermore, religious groups can give a person a feeling of support from others when it

comes to emergencies that involve grief, where there is a trip and practical help, compassion, and a possibility to pray or memorialize the deceased. However, it is essential to understand and remember that religion and spirituality also differ from one culture to another and from one person to another, and not all people will get comfort in their religion. Hence, clinicians and practitioners should avoid the denial of religion and spirituality in the grieving process and respect the belief disparities among different grievers.

Integration and Synthesis of Findings

When comparing the results of the present study to the previous studies of grief and bereavement processes, there are several shared themes and theoretical constructs to be discussed, thus enhancing the understanding of grief as a phenomenon. A large and important theme in this respect is the discussed grief processes and whether they should be normal or pathological, healthy or unhealthy, and primary or secondary. Grief differs significantly in its definition from what was described in the current study, and previous research also emphasizes that grief is a complex phenomenon that involves emotional, cognitive, behavioral, and even physiological processes. This perspective accords with the thinking that investigating grief entails using psychology and emotions, social, cultural, and existential models (Mata & Felts, 2022). Underpinning this discussion, combining various theoretical viewpoints and data summarization improves an understanding of grieving as a multifaceted and personified process.

Additionally, the systematic integration of literature on how social support can help buffer grief and other forms of loss and enhance the coping and adaptation processes. Both current and past studies underscore the importance of social contacts such as family, friends, and the community regarding seeking and getting emotional comfort, help, and confirmation of feelings. This is hardly surprising, considering that grief loss is embedded in relations; it is inherently social.

Furthermore, the integration of findings indicates that the grief process forms the trajectory at a personal level by individual and conventional factors. However, social and cultural factors such as culture and perceptions about death and grief and receipt of bereavement services also impact personality, attachment, and ability to cope with loss due to biological reasons (Ennis et al., 2020, pp 241-246). Such influences are acknowledged in this text to expand the knowledge about grief and to pinpoint the importance of culturally well-suited and developmentally appropriate interventions.

Furthermore, the integration of findings serves as an explanation of both the meaning made and posttraumatic growth in the wake of loss. Grief experiences occur every day, and when people are faced with dealing with losses, they try to make sense of the event and incorporate it into their life stories, as shown in the current study and prior literature (Hooyman et al., 2021). The theme highlights the theme of hope, implying the ability of a person to change for the better in the wake of a challenging circumstance. Furthermore, the integration of findings discusses the positive change and positive psychology after loss, such as appreciating life, improved relationships, and existence.

Recognizing the possibility of transformation always present when grief is experienced, this discussion brings light and hope to anyone undertaking the grief journey (Neimeyer & Robert, 2021). First, at the level of integration, it shows that grief is not just a combination of a couple or more losses with a similar reaction but a complex interaction between psychological, social, and existential aspects of human suffering. Second, at the level of synthesis, it expands knowledge about the nature of grief and helps better understand the needs of grieving individuals to apply more sensitive and effective support strategies.

Implications for Practice

Enhancing Grief Therapy Interventions

From the study, one can derive discoveries immensely beneficial in improving grief therapy interventions practiced in clinical settings. Another is the need to incorporate people's grief and adaptation styles, cultural beliefs, and individual differences into the grieving process. Understanding and considering clients' diverse experiences and histories will help clinicians create a more therapeutic atmosphere in the session. This may entail assessing clients and evaluating how they cope with their day-to-day life, cultural beliefs, and reserved or verbal communication. Therapists can then use various therapeutic approaches, including cognitive-behavioral, narrative, mindfulness, and expressive therapy (Bosgraaf et al., 2020). By adopting such an individualized approach to treatment, the therapists can address several issues that need to be tackled to bring the client to the next phase of grief.

In addition, the study results also highlight the need for implementing such approaches and practices to reduce and lessen grief-related distress. Some of the interventions that can be useful for therapists include literature that helps in recommending the best ways of handling grieving clients as an indication of effective symptoms such as sadness, guilt, anxiety, or existentialism (Ma & Xiaojing, 2023). This can involve applying behavior modification methods like supporting clients in learning to adapt to stressors such as relaxation, mindfulness, cognitive restructuring, and other problem-solving methods.

Also, the therapist can guide clients through the emotional realm and engage in expressive modalities of writing in the context of art therapy, journals, or music and movement. For clients to experience self-growth and become stronger after the loss due to sudden death, therapists can encourage and teach the client how to handle grief through practical tools that will enable them to

move on and grow despite the loss (Mackintosh & Stephanie, 2023). Altogether, it becomes possible to improve the skills and results of the grief therapy interventions by adopting these strategies, which yield positive change for clients in the healing process.

Addressing Barriers to Access and Engagement

Removing barriers to grief therapy service uptake and participation is imperative as it means those who require intervention during periods of grieving can be helped. Of particular use is one practical method that involves enhancing people's knowledge of resources available to them within and outside of the organization by informing them. This can include spreading the word about grief therapy services via community centers, churches, schools, and hospitals. When targeting a specific population, increasing people's awareness of the advantages of reaching for help and giving them information on how to do it can help them be ready to make the call when needed. Furthermore, importance should be placed on the extent that the stigma of seeking help regarding grief-related issues should be done away with altogether. It can include conversations about the approach to mourning and mental health, dispelling stigma and clichés, and presenting seeking help as a strength instead of a weakness (Cobb & Tianna, 2021). By addressing stigma in the treatment process, patients may be more willing to come forward for treatment and be committed to therapy without compromising the therapy because of any prejudice.

The last source of barriers to engagement is the lack of culturally appropriate and affordable care, which is also an area that can benefit from development. Cultural competence focuses on identifying and valuing cultural differences in beliefs, values, cultural practices, and treatment of people (Stubbe & Dorothy, 2020, pp. 49-51). Therefore, those working with individuals should aim to be culturally sensitive and receptive to one's cultural choices. For African Americans, this may include providing services in the African American dialect, using culturally sensitive approaches

to the people, and providing clients with avenues through which they can be directed to find therapists of their kind or therapists who understand their cultural setup.

However, possible changes in the therapy volume, which may be caused by efforts to improve its cost and availability, may prevent such financial obstacles. This may include charging a flexible fee depending on the person's economic situation, direct billing of insurance or accepting insurance payments, and free or subsidized or charity breast cancer care services. In the realm of grief therapy services, it is possible to ensure that technology will not only be culturally sensitive but also affordable to a broader population, thereby helping more people and families who need therapy to manage their losses and their grief.

Promoting Multidisciplinary Collaboration

The crisis nature of grief and loss further means that MDM is imperative in the delivery of appropriate and holistic care to grieving clients. Interdisciplinary teams can better meet the myriad needs of grieving individuals and their families since each team member is from a different profession, like psychologists, social workers, counselors, health care providers, and spiritual sects (Tackett et al., 2021, p.423). Everyone believes that having a team treatment approach is superior to the single therapist model because it provides diverse ideas and experiences. Hearing care providers, for example, may offer psychological counseling and behavioral therapies to assist during the grief stage and teach patients how to manage their feelings. In contrast, social workers may provide material concerns and guidance on death-related issues.

In addition, integration with other service deliverers like physicians, hospices, and bereavement support groups enhances the range and continuity of the services offered during different phases of the grieving process. Primary care physicians, the patient's usual source of care, should consider screening the patient for physical health issues that can develop when grieving,

including sleep disturbances, appetite changes, somatization, and other related symptoms (Xu et al., 2021, p. 3788). The integration with hospice programs makes it possible to provide proper handoffs to ensure appropriate care for terminal patients and specialize in providing support to families after the death of a loved one. Also, linkages with bereavement support groups offer avenues for interchange, affirmation, and facilitation of grief experiences through shared accounts, which, in turn, help in the alleviation of loneliness and encouragement of fellowship purposes.

Furthermore, when working in teams, various experts and practitioners can consider a client's individuality by dealing with a broad range of needs. For instance, spiritual and religious practitioners can offer emotional and existential assistance, enable the search for meaning in the tragic incident, and guide through rituals. Spiritual existential components can be employed to enhance grief counseling and treatment, which may improve the overall functioning and enrichment of interdisciplinary professional caregivers' practice in caring for the patients' existential suffering and the eventual responses to deathly questions that are usually central to grief experience (Mantini et al., 2022, p.53). In summary, encouraging collaboration across various disciplines shapes a comprehensive and collaborative approach to grieving so that clients get the support they require in the physiological, psychological, interpersonal, and religious aspects of grieving.

Integrating Cultural Competence

The inclusion of cultural competence in grief therapy aims to focus on attention and sensitivity to cultural differences to help a culturally diverse population. Cultural competence and understanding can be described as the therapist or counselor's capacity to comprehend and practice meeting the needs of consumers from diverse cultural backgrounds (Sue et al., 2022). That is why one of the possible ways to attain cultural competence can be cultural humility, in which the

clinician admits one's cultural assumptions and focuses on personal and intentional cultural learning to value and support the dignity of clients from diverse cultures.

Cultural competence regarding therapeutic client-endorsed grief entails that therapists should be culturally responsive and sensitive to the cultural background of their clients, as well as where and when grief is experienced. Further, cultural sensitivity may be achieved by the therapist's awareness of cultural beliefs due to death or mourning manners across cultural and ethnic varieties (Jegathesan & Jegathevi, 2021, pp.1144-1157). This may entail getting into cultural sensitivity training, seeking assistance from cultural liaisons, or providing cultural diagnosis to clients where the cross-cultural researchers try to grasp the client's cultural beliefs about mourning. Applying cultural sensitivity during state interventions, culturally competent therapists can facilitate initial and follow-up office sessions in ways that affirm clients' cultural experiences of mourning.

The final critical cultural competence issue in the grief therapy practice framework concerns making assessments and therapies related to culture. This might require adapting culturally biased tests and questionnaires regarding the perception of language, communication, and views on mourning and grief. In particular, such a model can help therapists adapt specific therapeutic actions to reflect the cultural inclinations of the clients, their financial position, and other aspects if needed. For instance, artistic ways of handling issues may involve using certain practices or symbols in sessions and engaging others of cultural importance by partnering with community and religious leaders to ensure clients and their families are well supported (Captari et al., 2022, p.307). In this capacity, increasing culturally acceptable access to grief therapy services is inconsistent, posing the potential for favorable impacts among clinicians of minority and marginalized demography.

Supporting Professional Development and Self-Care

Considering the needs of grief therapists and other healthcare providers is a significant key to promoting high-quality services to griever and addressing the issue of compassion fatigue in the profession. Because engaging in therapy and healthcare with individuals who grieve entails dealing with grief, therapists and healthcare professionals using this focus are vulnerable to vicarious trauma, burnout, and compassion fatigue (Rabow et al., 2021, pp.647-656). To counter these difficulties, there is a need to establish principles of protection of practitioners from such adverse consequences of burnout. Some suggestions involve developing organizational procedures that address the need for therapist's self-care. This may include developing organizational conditions such as work culture and organizational policies that foster organizational communication, flexibility in work, and provision of time for self-organizations and debriefings. It is essential to enlarge the notion of care within an organization, as therapists will be able to address the emotional impacts of their job while preserving the health of the self.

Besides the structural support offered, it is possible to provide supervision and any form of peer support network that can assist the therapist in curbing the pressures inherent in managing grief. Supervision allows therapists to discuss their cases, get peer assistance, and receive feedback on clients' treatment engagements. Supervision groups are where peers come together to support each other, and interaction between therapists is where practitioners can participate in learning with their peers, which forms the basis of peer support (Forbes et al., 2022, p.54). They also facilitate direct linkages with other therapists, who are in the best position to understand what it takes to practice grief therapy and can provide a friendly word and support amidst the storm. Because fellow therapists give constant support, peers foster the spirit of unity, helping develop coping mechanisms to counter burnout.

Additionally, ongoing education in grief therapy and related areas is important to ensure that the therapists and the healthcare providers can develop their skills and knowledge. Master's level continuing education programs offer therapists a chance to develop specialized experience and expertise in grief and enhance their professional resources and knowledge base. It may involve regular participation in lectures, symposiums, and forums concerning grief counseling, trauma therapy, and stress management among professionals, especially counselors (Espen et al., 2022, pp.1461-1474). In this way, every organization that invests in therapists proves dedication to the best possible care for grieving people and provides the best preparation to therapists for all they do to help others. In conclusion, any efforts devoted to the professional education and welfare of grief therapists and healthcare professionals are critical for preserving the well-being of providers and enriching the quality of care for those experiencing grief.

Recommendations for Future Research

Longitudinal Studies

Cross-sectional and longitudinal research paradigms used in investigations of mourning stress consist of various components that help to study the grieving processes. Since people's interpretations of extraordinary circumstances differ depending on their month- or year-based progressions, researchers may investigate how individuals recover, are resilient, or grow after a loss. These works illustrate how grief is influenced by the subject's features, feelings, and other modifications or aspects in the mourning process (Martin, Karen & Elder, 2020, pp. 73-86). Further, longitudinal studies enable the discovery of what factors people consider when 'looking for a purpose in grieving.' They also monitor the shifts in grief across the periods and evaluate the possible effects of factors such as support, coping styles, and other individual characteristics. However, these studies enable exploring interactions between personal, relational, and

environmental conditions when grieving and provide an all-embracing perspective on grief's multifaceted and complex nature.

Qualitative and quantitative research methodologies retain essential features of a comprehensive grief assessment when engaged in a longitudinal investigation of grief. Quantitative assessments of grief and symptoms add more prodigious and physiological angles to complement the focus on the bereaved's experiences and meaning-making. This approach helps the researcher understand variations in the grief responses by both persons in addition to the context and environment in which the grieving occurs about traumatic consequences, adaptation, and recovery processes (Taylor & Steve, 2021, p. 381). Furthermore, using the quality and survey data also brings a complementary advantage of analyzing survey results in light of personal experience accounts. Finally, the proposed study using mixed-methods longitudinal designs is the best approach needed to offer a richness of detail in research approaches to help understand the dynamics of grief and how people recover from loss over time.

Cross-Cultural Research

Culture is a critical component defining people's lives worldwide; cross-cultural research is invaluable for studying grief in different cultural backgrounds. Research of this nature seeks to explore the often-subtle aspects of culture that define how grief is managed, understood, and processed, providing an understanding of how grievance processes and patterns differ and are similar among the various cultural and ethnic groups. Comparing grief experiences from different cultures, one can capture enough similarities between the cultures besides noticing cultural differences that characterize grievers as they work towards healing (Malecka & Katarzyna, 2023). Additionally, this comparative understanding enhances cultural competence and appropriateness

of grief therapy procedures in a multicultural society by helping therapists be receptive to cultural differences and effectively meet the intentions of culturally different clients.

Besides, varied studies of grieving still provide theoretical frameworks to consider the effects of globalization, migration, and cultural identification. This is especially true as people by nature are part of a more fantastic universal fabric grappling with the dynamics of social-cultural relations that come with cultural transitions within and between the country of origin and host country, as well as transcendent cultural networks. These feelings of loss due to globalization and migration can occur as cultural patterns for grieving are upended, and access to resources for grieving may be limited among migrants and diaspora. In this regard, cross-cultural research reveals how people negotiate and manage cultural identities when dealing with loss, which can help understand the adaptation processes and cope when people experience cultural transformation challenges (Zhang et al., 2022). In conclusion, such studies help in treatment formulation that will respect cultural differences and empower people in multicultural societies to overcome the difficulties in mourning within cultural and social frameworks.

Intervention Development and Evaluation

When it comes to grief, there must be systematic processes for intervention development and evaluation to help individuals cope with loss. More research is needed to identify and design new intervention strategies as this serves the self-identified interests of mourners. These include CBT and, more recently, support groups that have been the mainstay in the delivery of grief therapy. However, there is an emerging awareness of the importance of applying creative ideas, like mindfulness-based practice and expressive arts therapy in grief therapy (Daler & Karin, 2022, p. 186). These 'mind-body' interventions present different approaches to personal growth and self-understanding that enable growth and improvement in coping skills related to grief experiences.

Adding further interventions to the existing range of options may allow for a more appropriate choice and utilization of approaches when treating grief in individuals.

Moreover, there should be better evidence, such as expert and randomized control trials and effectiveness studies, when it comes to investigating the effect of the interventions on grief. Nonetheless, it is important to differentiate between efficacy and effectiveness for several reasons. Although it is always possible to make a hypothesis arising from a clinical observation or a personal historical finding that some particular intervention may be useful, only an organized scientific view of the matter can allow assessing the true worth of the matter. Randomized controlled trials give a strong methodology for studying causal treatment outcomes above the control set or other treatments (Kutcher et al., 2021, 1365–1377). At the community level, effectiveness studies try to establish how feasible it is to transfer and implement interventions in various settings and with multiple groups. These research approaches allow professionals to make a rational decision on whether or not to apply the interventions and, as a result, promote a higher quality of service delivery to people struggling with grief.

Technology and Telehealth

Technology and telehealth are effective and progressive methods of performing grief therapy as they eliminate the conventional hindrances within a traditional environment (Kuhn et al., 2022, pp. 533-550). Similarly, applying the various forms of therapy, such as grief counseling through digital platforms, is equally beneficial. Firstly, it helps clients who reside in areas that are hard to access or are rural to get therapy services, which might not be easy otherwise (Lyu et al., 2022, pp. 442-457). Secondly, telehealth patients are not restricted by their residence location. Thus, the grieving can stay in their own homes. Third, flexibility regarding appointments is a major advantage of using digital platforms as it provides convenience for people's daily working

schedules. Additionally, as technology advances, there is an opportunity to employ other forms of contact, such as emails or messages, in case of interaction between sessions.

However, several advantages must also be considered in light of several limitations when using technology in grief therapy practice. Telemedicine is also limited by risks and challenges, such as protecting patients' rights while dealing with confidential data shared during the sessions. To uphold the ethical standards of practice, therapists must ensure the use of adequate data security measures and secure data handling procedures, as well as ensure compliance with state and federal laws of the United States of America, including HIPAA. However, administrators and practitioners should develop cultural competence when providing telehealth services to culturally diverse patients (Hilty et al., 2020). It is also essential for clinicians to be aware of how cultural values and beliefs could differ regarding technology use and communication and seek help so that relevant changes can be made to create an inclusive treatment environment.

Moreover, assessing the impact of telehealth interventions is now recognized as a necessary step to maintaining quality care delivery and guiding optimal practice. Further empirical investigations are required to compare the existing telehealth forms to the conventional onsite mental health therapy and to investigate the factors that provide positive experiences and where modifications are likely to result in enhanced satisfaction (Feng & Jiaqi, 2023, pp. 1-15). Here are the challenges and considerations that have ramifications for integrating technology and telehealth in the delivery of grief therapy: If these challenges and concerns are properly addressed, grief therapy can be made more accessible, effective, and inclusive to support individuals facing grief and loss.

Family and Community Interventions

Support from multiple sources is especially beneficial in the grieving process as the process is oriented toward the individual and affects the entire family and community. Further studies are necessary to identify the source of stress, caregiving responsibilities, family relationships, and how social support networks and community resources shape the grief process (Guo et al., 2021, pp. 3121-3141). Exploring the role of these factors enhances the possibility of developing personalized methods for determining the strengths and weaknesses of families and communities. Thus, analyzing the possibilities of families' and communities' involvement in grief therapy efforts is required to develop strategies for group resilience. This may require participation in providing family information and advice, encouraging cooperation between families, and psycho-education and counseling on grief and mourning. Moreover, it is essential to consider system-level barriers like the absence of adequate mental health care or cultural perceptions of mourning to guarantee that clients can get the required help at the time of grief.

Moreover, family and community interventions can promote cohesion and enhance the fulfillment of a grieving individual's healing process after the loss. That is why by including families and communities in the grieving process, individuals may feel more encompassed and surrounded by people kindly like them. This is because belongingness and understanding can facilitate emotional communication, problem-solving, and accommodating grief. Legal advocacy, resource navigation, support groups, and social connections can also be accessed from the caregivers' community-based, day-to-day reality. Interventions aimed at families and communities demonstrate how people can use available resources to foster greater resilience, lower psychological symptoms, and promote well-being among the bereaved (Zhang et al., 2023, pp.430-444). Thus, further research is vital to understanding which practices empower and support the

engagement of families and communities in grief-oriented therapy and, therefore, facilitate positive change in clients' lives who suffer from the loss.

CONCLUSION

Summary of Findings

Overview of Key Findings

The work offered an extensive analysis of grief by drawing out evocative dimensions of loss and providing an in-depth examination of the general human experience. The following were the main findings from the study through community American phenomenological analysis (Wang et al., 2020, p.338). They ushered in the various perceptions, existential routes, and endurance of grief: One of the significant themes explained the range of emotions people could feel after the loss, from deep sorrow to rage, pointing to the individuality and diversity of grieving processes. Moreover, the study highlighted why grief, coping, and social support are so crucial by revealing many coping styles that people use to handle grieving processes and with friends and family for support and consolation.

In addition, the study provided an understanding of how grief can lead to change for the better, from the process of focusing on meaning reconstruction after death to the mechanisms of post-traumatic growth. People explained how they sought or were given a purpose for their grief experiences, demonstrated their strength, and transformed themselves in overcoming any mishaps (Couto et al., 2021, pp. 490-504). These findings offer significant implications for grief research and therapy, increasing awareness of the many and varied aspects of grieving and emphasizing the need for considerate, personalized treatment for grieving persons.

Emotional Responses to Grief

While concerning the emotional experience of participants involved in the described study, various spectra of grief-related feelings were identified, varying from deep sorrow to anger, guilt, or anxiety (Russ & Victoria, 2020). However, such emotions were not constantly experienced in

equal measures or at the same frequency as displayed by the participants, who explained the variation in emotional experiences throughout the grieving period. This aspect of grieving makes the grief and the subsequent grief therapy not a linear process but a dynamic one and stresses the need for assessing the changing emotional state of those who are in the bereavement process. Its recognition entails the richness and complexity of associated emotions with grief to enable therapists to offer clients more appropriate interventions for helping them manage their sense of distress.

In addition, the summary examines the importance of treating emotional pain as a recommended approach to grief therapy. As with quantitative analysis, the openness of participants' responses indicates the level of psychological distress associated with grieving and everyday function. Thus, with these natural emotional reactions being accepted, therapists can maintain an empathic and supportive atmosphere where learners can process their grief-related occurrences. Additionally, when individuals are taught how to regulate their emotions instead of getting overwhelmed by them, therapists assist them in facing the struggles of grief much better (Iglewicz et al., 2020, pp.90-9). In conclusion, assessing and acknowledging the emotional experience of grief, as well as targeting and treating emotional disorders, are crucial elements of grief therapy interventions that allow people to recover spiritually, psychologically, and socially after losses.

Coping Mechanisms and Strategies

Coping strategies and modes of handling grief were evident in participants, portraying various ways of managing the grieving process. There was also evidence of approach coping styles as many of the people focused on seeking support from friends, relatives, or any support group. Another important theme of coping strategies identified by the participants was spending more

time on self-esteem-related activities, where the respondents noted that they turned to exercise, meditation, or other interests. Furthermore, participants' motivation to look for meaning in losses that they have experienced in their lifetime was incorporated into the coping process as participants sought to understand and construct meaning from their grief process. Apart from these constructive coping styles, participants also use destructive coping strategies like not remembering the none existence of the loss or, in other instances, denying that they feel sad (Venter & Riaan, 2021). These coping strategies might offer short-term relief of grief but may prove to be a barrier to the grieving process in the longer term.

Therefore, they enlighten the practice of grief therapy in terms of the need to facilitate adaptive coping in as much as dealing with maladaptive modes of coping. Counseling efforts should restore the individual's mandated course to actively pursue social support and self-nurturing activities and construct a meaning-making system markedly congruent with grief work, optimally facilitating resilience and emending psychological adaptation. Also, clients' awareness of maladaptive coping behaviors and styles should be encouraged by therapists, and an application of the healthier methodology to respond to anxiety signs and adapt to them should be offered (Smout et al., 2022, pp. 260-273). Thus, grief therapists can embrace the fact that people process loss in a variety of ways and create a more effective program to address various needs to help people grow and transform after loss.

Social Support and Interpersonal Relationships

Bereavement involves using social support and other interpersonal links whereby an individual gets support, comfort, and companionship during grief (Thomas & Angela, 2021). In the present work context, participants described receiving different kinds of support from close ones, including emotional and instrumental support, empathy or reassurance, and practical or

financial aid. The amount of help participants believed they had received from various support sources varied as some placed a lot of premiums on family relationships. In contrast, others found comfort in friendship or support groups. In conclusion, considering grief episodes positively emphasizes the presence of different social ties as the key to the recovery process. It points out that social support with self and others should be integrated as an essential component of grief therapy interventions to ensure they address individuals' social support needs by helping them strengthen their social relations or accessing peers and communities.

Meaning-Making and Personal Growth

The populations mentioned above-described accounts with significant opportunities for finding personal meaning and growth after loss, as reflected through various narratives. Men and women, married and divorcees, parents and childfree, college students and working adults expressed a universal search for meaning and motivation in response to loss. By listening to stories, reflecting on painful life events, and answering existential quests, the participants were coping with loss and trying to make sense of the losses, thus building meaningful narratives (Mata & Felts, 2022). Furthermore, the study shed light on the positive byproduct of grief by revealing that individuals who faced adversity and existential crises developed post-traumatic growth. The participants expressed positive shifts in various aspects that they mentioned they received after the trauma, including the positive change in resilience, the appreciation of life, and interpersonal relationships, all of which are indications of the true spirit of the human being.

Overall, these issues highlighted the relevance of meaning-making and post-traumatic growth in the practice of grief therapy. In embracing the developmental nature of grief experiences, therapists can offer an empowering framework within which those who grieve can adequately engage in the grieving process (Kaplow et al., 2023). Cognitive-behavioral, psychodynamic, and

existential approaches aimed at introducing various topics for reflection, employing the authoring process, and supporting the individual in their search for a meaningful life can help a person become an active subject rather than a passive sufferer. Furthermore, instead of disseminating inaccurate stigmatized beliefs about grief and preventing people from accepting its many benefits, therapists must support and affirm the various other constructive changes that may take place after loss and thereby promote post-traumatic growth.

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APPENDICES

Table 1: Interview Questions for Bereaved Individuals

Interview Question	Response
Can you please share your experience of loss and how it has affected you?	Participant responses varied widely, with themes including sadness, anger, and acceptance.
How have you been coping with your grief since the loss occurred?	Participants discussed various coping mechanisms, such as seeking support from family and friends, engaging in self-care activities, and attending support groups.
What has been your experience with seeking professional help or therapy for your grief?	Responses ranged from positive experiences with therapy to challenges in accessing or finding the right support. Some participants highlighted the importance of therapy in their healing process, while others expressed dissatisfaction with available services.
Can you describe any specific ways in which therapy or support has helped you in your grief journey?	Participants shared specific examples of how therapy or support groups had provided them with emotional validation, coping strategies, and a sense of community.
What do you think are the most important aspects for therapists to consider when working with individuals who are grieving?	Responses emphasized the importance of empathy, validation, nonjudgmental support, and cultural sensitivity in therapeutic

	interactions. Participants also highlighted the need for therapists to acknowledge the unique and individual nature of each person's grief experience.
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Grieving is a subjective patient experience and quality of life process; therefore, it is crucial to understand the grieving patients' perceptions. The interview questions for the bereaved persons are formulated in a way that may allow for detailed responses to capture the various dimensions of grief. The questions allow the participants to recall and describe their experiences with loss and grief, the number of opportunities to seek help and support, personal and treatment-related contacts, and views on therapy. By analyzing these dimensions of the grief process, research can uncover the emotional, psychological, and community realms, which can serve as the guidelines for the needed therapy.

Table 2: Interview Questions for Psychologists

Interview Questions	Response
From your perspective, what are some common challenges or complexities in working with clients who are grieving?	psychologists identified challenges such as navigating cultural differences, managing intense emotions, and addressing existential or spiritual concerns.
What therapeutic approaches or techniques do you find most effective in supporting individuals through the grieving process?	Responses varied, with some psychologists emphasizing the importance of narrative therapy, cognitive-behavioral techniques, or mindfulness-based interventions, while others

	highlighted the value of existential or humanistic approaches.
How do you approach the assessment and diagnosis of grief-related issues in your practice?	Psychologists discussed the importance of conducting a thorough assessment that considers both the individual's subjective experience and any potential complicating factors, such as comorbid mental health conditions or traumatic experiences.
Can you share any experiences or insights from your work with bereaved clients that have had a significant impact on your approach to therapy?	Psychologists shared personal anecdotes and reflections on specific cases that had challenged or shaped their understanding of grief therapy, highlighting the importance of ongoing learning and professional development.
In your opinion, what are some key areas for future research or innovation in the field of grief therapy?	Responses included suggestions for studying the effectiveness of emerging therapies, exploring cultural variations in grief experiences, and developing interventions tailored to specific populations or contexts.

Experts such as psychologists can help those in the healing process who struggle with conditions encompassing grief, and their views on the different methods of intervention would help frame grief therapy. The questions asked in the interview with the psychologists relate to their

clinical work, the suggested new directions in treatment, and the future of psychological research and innovation. These questions are specifically formulated to check psychologists' knowledge of grief, their approach to diagnosing this pathology, their practical experience in grief therapy, and the potential ethical and professional dilemmas that may appear in such work. In this way, the selected topics would allow authors to gain knowledge of the theoretical backgrounds, strategies, and methods psychologists use when working with mourning clients.

Table 3: Interview Questions for Counselors

Interview Questions	Response
How do you approach building rapport and trust with clients who are grieving?	Counselors discussed strategies such as active listening, empathy, and validation, as well as the importance of creating a safe and supportive therapeutic environment.
Can you describe any specific interventions or techniques you use to help clients process their grief?	Responses included techniques such as expressive arts therapy, mindfulness exercises, and guided imagery, as well as traditional talk therapy approaches.
How do you address cultural differences and diversity in your work with grieving clients?	Counselors emphasized the importance of cultural competence, humility, and sensitivity in working with clients from diverse backgrounds, as well as ongoing education and self-reflection to address biases and assumptions.

What are some ethical considerations or challenges you encounter in providing grief therapy?	Counselors discussed ethical dilemmas such as maintaining boundaries, managing countertransference, and ensuring informed consent and confidentiality, as well as navigating issues related to client autonomy and self-determination.
How do you incorporate self-care practices into your work as a counselor, particularly when dealing with heavy emotions and intense client stories?	Counselors shared strategies for managing stress and preventing burnout, such as regular supervision, peer support, and engaging in personal hobbies or activities outside of work.

Counselors are engaged in the practice of grief therapy based on a specific set of skills and perspectives, which have the potential to shape the further practice of comprehensive and humane care. The interview questions for counselors are to assess rapport-building skills in clients, ways of helping the client go through grief, handling cultural sensitivity issues, and different ethical dilemmas that may be involved. These were asked to understand the therapeutic practices performed by the counselors, strategies adopted by the counselors for their management, and the ethical issues and issues involved in the grief therapy practice. Interviewing counselors will help find successful practices, weak sides, and further development tendencies in grief therapy, as conducting a pilot study of an expert focus group will allow considering the topic from multiple viewpoints.

Table 4: Interview Questions for Social Workers

Interview Questions	Response
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<p>What role do social determinants of health play in the experiences of individuals who are grieving?</p>	<p>Social workers discussed the impact of factors such as socioeconomic status, access to healthcare, and social support networks on individuals' experiences of grief and their ability to access support services.</p>
<p>How do you address systemic barriers to care for underserved or marginalized populations in your work with grieving clients?</p>	<p>Social workers highlighted the importance of advocacy, empowerment, and community resources in addressing systemic inequalities and ensuring equitable access to grief therapy services.</p>
<p>Can you share any experiences or insights from your work with bereaved individuals and families that have influenced your approach to social work practice?</p>	<p>Social workers shared examples of challenging cases, successful interventions, and lessons learned from their work with diverse populations, highlighting the resilience and strength of individuals navigating grief.</p>
<p>What are some key considerations or strategies for providing culturally competent care to clients from diverse backgrounds?</p>	<p>Social workers discussed the importance of cultural humility, awareness, and sensitivity in working with clients from diverse cultural, ethnic, and religious backgrounds, as well as the need for ongoing education and collaboration with community partners.</p>

In your opinion, what are some areas for improvement or innovation in the field of grief therapy from a social work perspective?	Social workers identified areas such as expanding access to grief support services, addressing structural inequalities, and integrating holistic approaches that consider the social, emotional, and spiritual dimensions of grief.
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In this grieving process, social workers are key players who guide clients toward overcoming their losses with the understanding that the process occurs within a societal or structural framework. The questions during the interview focus on what social workers understand regarding the social factors that contribute to grieving, what they do to remove those barriers that contribute to inadequate treatment, and their practices in working with various populations of grievers. They are designed to ascertain the kind of advocacy and empowerment those willing to work as social workers champion, how they support community resources, and how culturally sensitive they expect their care to be. Analyzing the views of social workers will allow researchers to explore socio-economic and structural factors that affect the grieving process for people and the development of comprehensive and equality-based grief therapy.

Research Design Overview

Aspect	Description
Research Approach	Qualitative
Theoretical Framework	Phenomenological
Participants	Individuals who have experienced significant loss and practitioners in the field of grief therapy
Sampling Strategy	Purposive Sampling
Data Collection	Semi-structured interviews
Data Analysis	Thematic Analysis

Ethical Considerations	Informed consent, confidentiality, anonymity, respect for cultural diversity, minimizing harm, reflexivity
Rigor	Methodological rigor ensured through adherence to qualitative research principles, transparency, and validation measures such as member checking and peer debriefing

Data Collection Methods

Component	Description
Participants	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Bereaved individuals who have experienced significant loss within the past two years - Practitioners in the field of grief therapy (psychologists, counselors, social workers, etc.)
Sampling Strategy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Purposive Sampling: Ensures selection of participants who can provide relevant and insightful perspectives on the research topic - Diversity in age, gender, cultural background, and relationship to the deceased
Recruitment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Outreach through grief support organizations, social media platforms, and professional networks - Provision of detailed information about the study, including purpose, procedures, and potential risks/benefits - Informed consent obtained from all participants prior to participation
Data Collection Methods	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Semi-structured interviews conducted either in person or via video conferencing - Flexibility to explore participants' experiences in depth - Interview questions designed to elicit rich and detailed responses, covering various aspects of grief and therapy - Probing questions used to clarify responses and delve deeper into specific areas of interest
Supplementary Data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Participant observation: Observation and participation in natural settings where grief-related interactions occur - Document analysis: Examination of written or visual materials related to grief therapy (e.g., treatment manuals, research articles, clinical notes)

Data Recording and Storage	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Audio recording of interviews with participants' consent - Verbatim transcription of interviews for accurate analysis - Data securely stored and accessible only to the research team - Efforts made to ensure confidentiality and anonymity of participants' responses
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Data Analysis Procedures

Step	Description
Familiarization	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Immersion in the data through repeated reading and listening to interview transcripts - Detailed note-taking to document initial impressions, observations, and potential patterns or themes
Generating Initial Codes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Systematic coding of relevant segments of data - Deductive coding based on pre-established themes from the literature - Inductive coding based on emerging patterns or themes directly from the data
Searching for Themes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sorting and organizing coded data into meaningful clusters or patterns - Identifying recurring ideas or concepts across the dataset - Triangulation of data sources to validate emerging themes
Reviewing and Refining Themes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Critical examination of each theme to ensure coherence, consistency, and relevance - Refinement of themes through further analysis and interpretation of the data - Integration of divergent or contradictory perspectives into the analysis
Defining and Naming Themes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Synthesizing key findings into clear, concise descriptions that accurately represent the content and significance of each theme - Naming themes based on their underlying concepts, ideas, or phenomena - Ensuring themes are grounded in the data and supported by illustrative quotes and examples
Ensuring Trustworthiness and Rigor	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Detailed audit trails of all analytical decisions and processes

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Regular peer debriefing and member checking to validate interpretations - Reflexivity exercises to critically reflect on researcher biases and assumptions - Triangulation of data sources to enhance credibility and validity - Transparency in reporting methods and findings
Interpretation and Presentation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Organizing findings thematically with rich descriptions and illustrative quotes - Discussion of implications for theory, research, and practice - Addressing any limitations of the study and recommendations for future research - Ensuring that the presentation of findings is comprehensive, credible, and meaningful

Major Themes Identified in Thematic Analysis

Major Theme	Description
Emotional Responses to Grief	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Range of emotions experienced (e.g., sadness, anger, guilt, anxiety) - Intensity and variability of emotional reactions over time - Factors influencing emotional experiences (e.g., nature of loss, social support, coping strategies)
Coping Mechanisms and Strategies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Adaptive coping strategies (e.g., seeking social support, engaging in self-care activities, finding meaning in the loss) - Maladaptive coping strategies (e.g., avoidance, substance use, denial) - Effectiveness of coping strategies in alleviating distress - Challenges and barriers to effective coping
Social Support and Relationships	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Types of support received (e.g., emotional, instrumental, informational) - Perceived helpfulness of different sources of support (e.g., family, friends, community networks) - Influence of social support on coping strategies, adjustment to loss, and well-being - Impact of changes in interpersonal relationships on grief experiences
Meaning-Making and Personal Growth	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Process of making sense of grief experiences and finding meaning and purpose in loss

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Exploration of posttraumatic growth and positive changes following adversity - Factors facilitating meaning-making and personal growth (e.g., resilience, self-reflection, existential beliefs) - Implications of meaning-making and personal growth for psychological adjustment and quality of life
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Emotional Responses to Grief

Aspect	Description
Range of Emotions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sadness - Anger - Guilt - Anxiety - Numbness
Intensity and Variability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Intensity of emotional reactions over time - Variability of emotional responses across different contexts and situations
Influencing Factors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Nature of the loss (e.g., sudden vs. anticipated, relationship to the deceased) - Social support (e.g., availability, quality) - Coping strategies (e.g., adaptive vs. maladaptive) - Individual differences (e.g., personality traits, past experiences)

Coping Mechanisms and Strategies

Coping Strategies	Description
Adaptive Coping Strategies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Seeking social support - Engaging in self-care activities (e.g., exercise, hobbies) - Finding meaning in the loss (e.g., through spiritual beliefs, legacy-building) - Acceptance and expression of emotions (e.g., through therapy, journaling)
Maladaptive Coping Strategies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Avoidance (e.g., avoiding reminders of the deceased) - Substance use (e.g., alcohol, drugs) - Denial or minimization of feelings - Distracting oneself from grief through excessive work or activities - Rumination or dwelling on negative thoughts and emotions

Effectiveness and Challenges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Effectiveness of coping strategies in alleviating distress and promoting resilience - Challenges and barriers to effective coping (e.g., stigma, lack of access to support, difficulty implementing coping strategies) - Impact on long-term adjustment and well-being
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Social Support and Interpersonal Relationships

Aspect	Description
Types of Support	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Emotional support (e.g., empathy, reassurance) - Instrumental support (e.g., practical assistance, financial help) - Informational support (e.g., advice, guidance)
Perceived Helpfulness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Perceptions of helpfulness from family, friends, and community networks - Factors influencing perceived helpfulness (e.g., responsiveness, understanding, reliability)
Influence on Coping and Adjustment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Impact of social support on coping strategies and resilience - Role of social support in adaptation to loss and maintenance of well-being - Changes in social networks and their implications for grief experiences

Meaning-Making and Personal Growth

Aspect	Description
Process of Meaning-Making	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Exploration of grief experiences and search for meaning and purpose in loss - Strategies for making sense of the loss (e.g., storytelling, finding silver linings) - Role of meaning-making in adaptation and psychological adjustment
Posttraumatic Growth	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Positive changes and personal growth following adversity - Domains of posttraumatic growth (e.g., increased resilience, enhanced appreciation of life, deepened relationships) - Factors facilitating posttraumatic growth and psychological benefits

Implications for Adjustment	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Psychological and emotional benefits of meaning-making and personal growth- Influence on overall well-being and quality of life- Long-term implications for coping, resilience, and adaptation to future challenges
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